

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC GRANT AGREEMENT NO. 676550

DELIVERABLE REPORT

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Deliverable Title	Workshops held within the 4 regions of primary interest
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Responsible Partner	BBMRI-ERIC
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WORKSHOPS HELD WITHIN THE 4 REGIONS OF PRIMARY INTEREST

Executive Summary

BBMRI-ERIC established itself in years as one of the key global players in the field of biobanking. While the main focus of BBMRI remains Europe, the organisation understand the need to expand its outreach outside the EU, and to set up a coherent global strategy to develop the field of biobanking globally, and to increase BBMRI's outreach.

The ADOPT-BBMRI project allowed to expand BBMRI's supporting biobanking activities in different regions in the world, and to develop a multi-year strategy, that represents the backbone of future BBMRI global action.

Within the project, BBMRI identified four key regions of primary interest: China, Africa, Middle East and the Americas (USA, Latin America). The implementation of the strategy in the regions was paired with existing BBMRI National Nodes activities and connections, therefore maximising the impact of the ADOPT-BBMRI funding. In particular, several of the workshops organised within the project were co-funded by activities of National Nodes within such regions.

ADOPT-BBMRI helped to bring the global biobanking community together, and highlighted the need for more international cooperation, based on the centres of excellence and networks identified by BBMRI.

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Document log

Issue	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Comment	Author/partner
D8.2_rev1	2019-03-01	Initial version of the report	Erik Steinfelder, Anna-Liisa Bader
D8.2_rev2	2019-11-11	Revised version of the report according to reviewer's comments	Francesco Florindi

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Background

Biobanking is a critical component of new treatments development, particularly personalised medicine. International clinical research collaboration has been essential to connect the best health researchers and ensure progress. However, to perform top notch personalised medicine it is necessary to have access to the best research infrastructures, including biobanks. While researchers can circulate now more than ever, samples are still collected and stored locally. Therefore, for the full development of personalised medicine globally, it is pivotal to develop a global network of biobankers, to promote the highest standards and best practices in biobanking in different regions, not only the USA and Europe. Within ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC we focused on 4 promising regions: China, Africa's low-/middle-income countries, North America and the Middle East.

During the project's lifetime, we realised the untapped potential for the Latin American region, and therefore we decided to amend the original plan and include it into the ADOPT project. While Latin American researchers and biobankers share a common language that it became evident that the community remained disconnected, therefore the concentration shifted in the end of the project to that specific region.

Approaches (Methods)

To make effective use of scarce resources, BBMRI-ERIC and its National Nodes agreed not to develop and fund the workshops from the sole budget of ADOPT-BBMRI, but to make use of existing collaborations of our National Nodes and leverage co-funding at the national level. This was possible thanks to the full co-operation of the BBMRI-ERIC Management Committee (which unites all National Node directors) and the direct engagement of key National Nodes. The result was that one workshop was co-funded by IARC and the symposium and workshop in Izmir was co-organised by BBMRI-ERIC in partnership with the BBMRI.tr node.

The Management Committee also played a crucial role in the development of the scientific programme of the workshop, providing fruitful insight and expert keynote speakers.

Results

Within the first year two workshops were co-funded, the EuroMed workshop in Malta for the Eastern Mediterranean Regions and a Train-the-Trainer workshop on Quality in France.

Within the second year only one workshop was co-funded, the IARC-BCNet – BBMRI-ERIC – Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians (22-23 May 2017) for Africans. Subsequently, a workshop and Symposium in Izmir for Middle-East was organized by BBMRI.tr, the Turkish Node of BBMRI-ERIC.

During the extension period of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC a workshop was organized for Latin-American biobankers in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

EuroMed workshop (18 March 2016)

In close cooperation with the Malta Node BBMRI.mt, a first workshop for the European-Mediterranean Region was held in Malta on March 18, 2016. Participants of this workshop came from BBMRI-ERIC as well as representatives from Tunisia, Morocco, Jordan, Cyprus and Spain. BBMRI-ERIC was introduced to those country delegates and potential collaborative activities discussed (Appendix 1-2).

Main outcome

The workshop mainly explored two key issues:

- Status of biobanking in the countries represented
- Opportunities for collaboration between BBMRI-ERIC, its National Nodes, and the countries represented.

Status of biobanking EuroMed

Through the presentations from the different representatives from EuroMed countries, several patterns and joint issues emerged:

- Important role of rare disease and cancer: each country has one or more biobanks focusing on oncology or rare disease samples. This narrows down large future cooperation to a few fields, while other disease areas offer ad hoc collaboration with specific collections.
- Sustainability: without international collaboration, several biobanks will face sustainability problems and funding issues. In this perspective, the workshop discussed specific opportunities for funding at the EU and global levels.

Opportunities for collaboration

Several practical opportunities for collaboration were underlined during the workshop. COST actions and ERASMUS+ programmes can be helpful to establish training programmes and foster knowledge exchange.

[Appendix 1. EuroMed meeting Agenda, Minutes and attendance list](#)

Quality conference and workshop (17-19 May 2016)

Based on the 3 MoUs with Chinese regions we have organized with BBMRI.fr and BBMRI.at a quality implementation workshop in Nice in timely accordance with the French Quality conference from May 17-19, 2016: Quality Matters (<http://www.biobanques.eu/fr/meeting-2016>).

Main outcome

The workshop focused on quality management and standardisation, key factors in the successful international scientific collaboration in biobanking.

Seven Chinese trainers were invited, but unfortunately because of visa issues not all could come or attend the workshop.

In the next [link](#) a video of the presentations is available.

[Appendix 2. Quality meeting agenda and workshop agenda](#)

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Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians (22-24 May 2017)

The workshop was co-organised by IARC and BBMRI-ERIC in the form of a training tailor-made to pathologists and biobankers from non-EU countries. The training took place in Cairo/Egypt, targeting African countries. Nearly 40 scientists and technicians were trained.

Main outcome

The programme focused on the key relationship between the figure of the pathologist and that of the biobanker, which is crucial to ensure the health, survival and sustainability of biobanks globally. The training featured high-level speakers from the BBMRI-ERIC European network.

[Appendix 3. Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians Agenda and attendance list](#)

Symposium: Bridging biobanks in MENA countries to promote research and Healthcare and Workshop on Biobanking for Rare Diseases (2-4 May 2018)

Organised by BBMRI.tr and hosted by the Izmir Biomedicine and Genome Center, the symposium and workshop brought together a total of 132 participants and experts from 14 different countries. The aim was to establish and strengthen existing collaborative biobanking networks in MENA countries, as well as to facilitate their integration with pan-European counterparts.

Main outcome

The workshop focused on rare disease, a topical area of common interest between the MENA region researchers and BBMRI and explored in detail all the main issues related to the establishment, management and development of rare disease biobanks. On day 1, the participants were introduced to a general framework on biobanking, based on the three pillars of BBMRI services (quality, IT, ethical/legal/societal issues). Day 2 explored more in detail specific issues related to biobanking in rare disease.

The symposium (on day 3) allowed the MENA countries' biobanking experts to showcase the potential of connecting and working together with BBMRI, therefore highlighting the need for policymakers to keep sustaining biobanking and personalised medicine in MENA countries.

[Appendix 4. Bridging biobanks in MENA countries to promote research and Healthcare and Workshop on Biobanking for Rare Diseases Agenda](#)

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC Biobanking workshop in Latin America

Organised by BBMRI HQ, the workshop brought together 60 biobankers from 6 Latin American countries to share first-hand experience and establish connections between local biobanks and the European infrastructure.

On day one, we focused on the role of biobanking in modern medicine. Presenters from European biobanks, hospitals and universities shared their experiences. Examples of fully automated large-scale

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biobanking, the power of small collections for very specific studies, the need for automation, high quality and the willingness of sharing samples were presented and triggered lively debates among the attendees.

The meeting was structured to be interactive and to stir debate and questions from the audience. The key example is ‘the beer distribution game’, which let participants experience typical coordination problems of traditional supply chains (like the biobanking workflow), in which information sharing and collaboration exists minimally or not at all, often caused by lack of systemic thinking.

BBMRI-ERIC also collected crucial information about biobanking in Latin America currently. Participants had the opportunity to present their own biobank and work in short presentations, which showed that there is a lot of good work already in place, but the infrastructure or overall network is missing to keep the connections and dialogue going.

On the last day the group visited the LDAP labs URFJ, famous for its doping control lab work during the 2016 Summer Olympics in Rio. A clear vision and mission of the activities in combination with a highly committed team makes this a first-class facility and one of the two WADA accredited labs in the southern hemisphere.

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC provided a great opportunity to meet and share challenges and expectations. It is now the time to act. That’s why BBMRI-ERIC facilitated the creation of a pan-Latin American action list to build on the momentum set by ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC and create a more stable continental collaboration on biobanking. Volunteers from Brazil, Argentina, Mexico and Chili stepped forward to coordinate and lead the dialogue on biobanking in the region and make the first steps in giving the freshly built network a shape and a body.

[Appendix 5. ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC Biobanking workshop in Latin America Agenda and attendance lists and presentations](#)

Next Steps

Through ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC, we at BBMRI-ERIC aimed at increasing strategic research cooperation between different regions. For this to happen, BBMRI-ERIC had to identify reliable international communities of biobankers, and share information and knowledge to develop such communities.

While the European biobanking community is strong and united in Europe under the umbrella of BBMRI-ERIC, the same cannot be said for other world regions. Local centres of excellence and well-developed biobanks can provide the prodromes of future hubs for the creation of more solid communities that can become long-term partners of BBMRI-ERIC. ADOPT-BBMRI workshops provided a great starting point to establish or reinvigorate regional communities of biobankers, therefore facilitating and supporting the creation or strengthening of international strategic cooperation (within non-EU countries, and between EU/non-EU countries).

To sustain the success of the workshops and increase BBMRI-ERIC visibility towards the international scientific community, further actions (conferences, special workshops, symposia etc) should be organized. Such meetings shall aim at further structuring and supporting regional/international biobanking communities, to provide BBMRI-ERIC with strong international partners.

Finally, capacity building grants (co-funded by the European institutions and the international countries interested) shall provide sustainable resources for the management and operation of new biobanking communities across the world.

BBMRI-ERIC will continue to ensure knowledge transfer with the regions involved, by keeping connections with the parties involved in the workshops, and ensuring that they will be involved in future BBMRI-ERIC international activities (for example: future proposals for funding calls; organization of future Europe or Global Biobank Week etc).

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: EUROMED Workshop

Agenda

BBMRI-ERIC, 2nd EUROMED Workshop

2016/03/18

Venues:

- IT Services Building VC Hall 102 (Building #34) Main Campus, University of Malta, Msida
- Transportation provided from the Grand Hotel Excelsior at 08:30 on the 18th to Msida Main Campus and back to Grand Excelsior after the meeting
- **Specific Objective:** Roadmap to a competitive, collaborative hub of genetics and biobanking in the Mediterranean
- **Welcoming dinner on the 17th of March:** at 18:00 a walk to St John's co-Cathedral from the Hotel Grand Excelsior, and visit of Caravaggio's beheading of St John (guided tour) followed by a short walking tour of Valletta. Transportation will be provided after Valletta tour to the silent city, the Old Capital Mdina where dinner is at 20:00 at Palazzo de Piro, www.palazzodepiro.com
Transportation is provided back to Grand Excelsior Hotel after dinner.

AGENDA

– 18 March 2016

09:00 – 09:15	Welcome and introduction	<i>Alex Felice and Constantinos Deltas</i>
09:15 – 09:45	Introduction to BBMRI-ERIC	<i>Jan-Eric Litton (Director General)</i>
09:45 – 10:00	Why and How to join BBMRI-ERIC	<i>Markus Pasterk (Administrative Director)</i>
10:00 – 12:00	Tour de table: What do we expect from BBMRI-ERIC	<i>Participants (8 min each) Chairs: Jan-Eric Litton and Alex Felice</i>
12:00 – 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 - 14:50	Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COST re-application/ H2020 participation • Construction of Euro-Med cohorts as random neonates for genetics epidemiology/ comparative population genomics and others (e.g. haemoglobinopathies, kidney, T2DM & DMD, colorectal cancer) 	<i>All Chair: Alex Felice</i>
14:50 - 15:00	Round-up and closing remarks	<i>Alex Felice</i>

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Map of Biobanks in the Mediterranean Region

BBMRI EUROMED Minutes

- 1) An introduction from different Countries
 - The second EuroMed workshop, first was in 2010.
- 2) Presentation of questionnaire & EuroMed map
- 3) Comments from Markus Pasterk and Jan-Eric Litton (BBMRI-ERIC)
- 4) A new neonatal collection
 - Collect 400 random newborn samples from each Mediterranean country (maybe new and maybe less), 400 genome sequences (WGS and comparative population genomics),
 - Cancers – BBMRI (Maxim – Jordan)
 Mediterranean cohorts for research – Globin, Diabetes, Renal, Colorectal cancer
- 5) A new improved and enriched COST application, a tangible outcome of meeting (September 2016).
- 6) WP8 Internationalisation – Markus Pasterk
 - COST Action and another proposal for funding – H2020 applications, very difficult to compete at this level, have to show prior achievement
 - Trial readiness – needs a level of commitment
 - How can we better train biobanking staff – short courses, law statistics
 - Mid-September BBMRI-ERIC organising European Biobanking week (EBW) jointly with ESBB.
 - A biobanking curriculum can be developed.
 - Master program – can be available for staff outside of BBMRI-ERIC.
 - Erasmus project – can apply for same funding – for training, can train, require training for researchers and biobankers.

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- ERN upcoming call – will help in collecting samples, can be done quite easily – who will be leader of ERN

Morocco

Dr Meriem Khyatti (Video Conference)

Pasteur Institute

- Limited biobanking activities in Morocco
- Collaboration with eg North Africa, mainly on cancer
- Morocco willing to share samples and data if available

Cyprus

Prof Constantinos Deltas (Present)

Molecular Medicine Research Centre, University of Cyprus

- Sharing data, finding ways to collaborate in tangible ways
- Through teaming project already collected information from many surrounding EuroMed Countries so should collate data with our questionnaire data. The template of the teaming application can be used for future applications.
- A small biobank : project for inherited kidney disorders. Difficulties with funding, Widespread participating teaming programs, an opportunity, idea to upgrade the molecular center to a center of excellence. Advanced partners involved BBMRI and MUG. Stage 1 was successful and 0.5M eur funding was gained. Stage 2 end of May. Awarded 500k Eur for business plan and research proposal for. A reachout to other countries to share data.

Serbia

Dr Sonja Pavlovic (Present)

Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade

- Roughly 40-50 collections existing in Serbia, on state owned institutes
 - o Well organized collections including DNA, cells, mononuclear cells, and tissue samples
 - o Involvement in RD connect and other projects, published papers with consortium working on rare cancers
 - o Sharing the samples with University of Washington in population studies
 - o They would like to join BBMRI-ERIC to improve the biobanking, in Serbia and become a partner in projects
 - o Are well connected with other Balkan countries (PGI, involved in genetic studies in the Balkan region)
 - A partner in 1000 partners project (PGI funding)
 - o Initiative started 2015, PGI introduced a method for whole genome sequencing
 - o Now collecting the samples in e.g. Bulgaria , Greece and Yugoslavia
- ☑ Aim to study population genetics and making a reference library
- ☑ Forum for Next generation genetics
 - Other activities in serbia: institutes working on other diseases, they also have their biobanks for RDs but not well organized. Geneticists are well connected and also Serbian institutes
 - LPC Forum introduced during EBW and invited Serbia

Turkey

Prof Nese Atabey (Present)

Izmir Biomedicine and Genome Center, Dokuz Eylul University

- Wish to become a full member of BBMRI-ERIC
- Several RD biobanks, tissue and DNA collections in different hospitals, Turkey working on harmonization of these sample collections. Trying to improve the quality of clinical biobanks. DNA samples from approx. 10 000 families (50 000 samples) from many types of tissues

- Neurodegenerative diseases, and other interests
- Initiative: Turkish Genome project, supported by Turkish government plan to have 10 000 normal DNA samples from healthy people sequenced
- Health data collection is hindered by difficulties to connect to the patient registries. The biggest cohort is 30 000, collected 10 y ago, have follow up information. Goal to find biomarkers for heart diseases. Work ongoing in coordinating patient data with the samples in the biobanks.

Libya

Ms Seham Eljali (Present) obo Dr Abdul Elnfati
University of Tripoli

- Interested in setting up a biobank in Libya. Focus on genetics and RDs.

Jordan

Dr Maxim Al-Ashhab (Not present)
King Hussein Cancer Center Biobank (KHCCBIO)

- Possibilities unknown what can be done in the Medit. Area.
- The main constraint in the past years has been how to share samples in terms of consent, how to send samples, different regulations, data associated to the samples

Sicily – Italy

Prof Mariluisa Lavitrano (Present)
BBMRI.it

- A collection on the population level, stored in the Shaka (?) biobank, all newborns collected. A collection of blood and derivatives, newborns since 30 years.

Spain

Dr Manuel Posada (Skype)
Director, Insitute of Rare Disease Research, Istituto de Salud Carlos III

Lebanon

Dr Pierre Zalloua (Skype)
Dean, Lebanon American University

- Logistics and support needed in order to establish biobanks, limited resources, biobanks will be small, EuroMed cohort would be an idea.
- Homogenizing the cohorts challenging, other concerns: long term visions, what to do with the cohort, what are the short/longterm questions e.g. first 5 years, next 5 years
- Funding challenges exist to have a cohort, funding needs also to be sustained.
- Currently in Lebanon, there is no national biobank, only a few commercial Biobanks / collections for business purposes.
- Work ongoing for CVDs, 12000 individuals collected and work ongoing for another cohort in trying to unite samples from 290 primary healthcare centers within the Ministry of Public Health into one large cohort
- There is a need for a national biobank, but this priority has been delayed due to parties interested in commercial biobanking
 - o Maybe the existing collections could be united into one big clinical collection (through 3 or 4 hospitals)
- ☑ Complex issue: every major university hospital want to have their own biobank, not willing to share. Not easy to engage doctors from the private sector. All doctors in primary health care facilities are doctors. Have access to full medical charts, records and visits. The best way is to try to unite the collections from primary health care centers (easiest and most efficient).
 - Pierre is on Ethics Board.

☐ The same problem with Cyprus. Hard to engage the doctors in the biobanking activities

ATTENDANCE LIST

Prof Nese Atabey	Izmir Biomedicine and Genome Center, Dokuz Eylul University	Turkey	
Prof Constantinos Deltas	Molecular Medicine Research Centre, University of Cyprus	Cyprus	
Dr Paraskevi Christofidou	Molecular Medicine Research Centre, University of Cyprus	Cyprus	
Dr Sonja Pavlovic	Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade	Serbia	
Dr Natasa Tosic	Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade	Serbia	
Ms Seham Eljali	University of Tripoli	Libya	
Prof Jan-Eric Litton	Director General BBMRI-ERIC		
Mr Markus Pasterk	Administrative Director BBMRI-ERIC		
Dr Outi Tornwall	EU Project Manager BBMRI-ERIC		
Dr Andrea Wutte	Quality Manager BBMRI-ERIC		NOT FOR LUNCH
Prof Alex Felice	BBMRI.mt		
Ms Joanna Vella	BBMRI.mt		NOT FOR LUNCH
Ms Esther Zammit	BBMRI.mt		
Dr Alexander Camilleri	BBMRI.mt		
Dr Luca Sangiorgi	Rizzoli Orthopaedic Unit, Bologna, Italy		
Dr Georges Dagher	BBMRI.fr		
Dr Lukasz Kozera	BBMRI.pl		
Dr Maimuna Mendy	IARC		
Dr Jasper Bovenberg	CS-ELSI		
Dr Deborah Mascalzoni	Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB), University of Uppsala		
Dr Gianluigi Zanetti	Centre for Advanced Studies, Research and Development, Sardinia		Not for lunch

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Appendix II - Quality meeting agenda and workshop agenda

Agenda

TUESDAY MAY 17, 2016		
10:00	Opening session : Welcome & Opening Remarks	Georges DAGHER
	Session 1 : Controlling preanalytical factors	Chair: Paul HOFMAN & Uwe OELMUELLER
10:00	Why it is mandatory to control the pre analytical phase in biobanking activity associated with personalized medicine projects?	Paul HOFMAN
10:30	Standardized improved pre-analytical workflows: the bridge to good quality samples for reliable analytical test results	Uwe OELMUELLER
11:00	Developing evidence-based preanalytical procedures in metabolomics.	Paola TURANO
11:30	Using tissue samples for quantitative protein and phosphoprotein analysis – critical considerations	Karl-Friedrich BECKER
12:00	How to define sample quality in rapidly developing field	Kurt ZATLOUKAL
12:30	U.S. perspective on developing biospecimen evidence-based practices	Helen MOORE
13 :00	Lunch break	
14:30	Session 2: The present and future of biobanking	
	Session 2A: Biobanking infrastructures	Chair: Peter WATSON & Erich WICHMAN
14:30	Pan European infrastructure BBMRI-ERIC	Jan-Eric LITTON
15:00	The Austrian national infrastructure	Kurt ZATLOUKAL
15:20	The French National Infrastructure	Georges DAGHER
15:40	The Italian National infrastructure	Maria Luisa LAVITRANO
16:00	The Spanish National infrastructure	Manuel MORENTE
16:20	The Beijing infrastructure	Peng WANG
16:40	Break	
17:00	Session 2B: Next Generation Biobanking	Chair: Georges DAGHER & Kurt ZATLOUKAL
17:00	Precision Public Health: the essential role of healthcare-integrated biobanks	Bill OLLIER Martin YUILLE
17:40	Next generation histology using next generation sequencing.	Joakim LUNDEBERG
18:00	Next Generation Biobanking	Paul HOFMAN
18:20	Sustainability of biobanking	Bruno CLEMENT
18:40	Open discussion	
20:00	Cocktail dinner	

WEDNESDAY MAY 18, 2016		
	Session 3: Quality control in Genomics	
9:00	Session 3A	Chair: Andres METSPALU & Bill OLLIER
9:00	Quality control for the quantification of gene expression biomarkers	Jens BJÖRKMAN
9:30	Total genomic solution for Biobanks, maximize the value of your specimen	Coralie VACHER
10:00	AnyGenes molecular platform for biomarkers profiling	Ben Youssef NAIMI
10:30	Coffee break	
11:00	Session 3B	Chair: Helen MOORE
11:00	Quality Control standard for nucleic acids	Jacques BONNET
11:30	RNA in Archive Tissues: Degradation Causes and Extraction Precautions	Giorgio STANTA
12:00	Discussion	
12:30	Lunch	
15:00	Session 4: Quality control in Biobanks	Chair: Annick BARTHELEIX & Peter WATSON
15:00	Evidence-based biobanking practices.	Jim VAUGHT
15:30	Quality control in a Brain Bank	Charles DUYCKAERTS
16:00	Phenotypes and samples in the Estonian Biobank: ensuring the quality and control.	Andres METSPALU
16:30	Molecular biology-based quality control program: High-quality biobanking in China	Liangliang RUAN
17:00	Quality as an ethical requirement	Manuel MORENTE
17:30	Free time	
18:00	Master in Biobanking. Toward a harmonized cursus and training (on invitation)	
19:30	BIOBANQUES SAB meeting (on invitation)	

THURSDAY MAY 19, 2016		
9:00	Session 5.	Chair: Bruno CLEMENT & Paola TURANO
9:00	Good practices in cell culture	Barbara PARODI
9:30	Quantitative detection of Mycoplasma by Real-Time PCR of a 1.5 kb fragment using degenerate universal primers targeting 16S rDNA.	Denis GERLIER

10:00	Pre-analytic processing of liquid samples in population cohorts in Germany	Erich WICHMAN	
10:30	Challenges in using liquid biopsies for precision medicine	Maria Grazia DAIDONE	
11:00	Coffee break		
11:30	Session 6	Chair: Maria-Luisa LAVITRANO & Peng WANG	
11:30	The question of quality and standardization for pre-analytics in histopathology, immunohistology and in situ hybridization testing.	Gilles ERB	
12:00	Metabolomics of tissues	Paola TURANO	
12:30	Liquid biopsies for metabolomics	Christophe JUNOT	
13:00	Lunch		
15:00	Session 7. Quality Assurance in Biobanking	Chair: Giorgio STANTA & Jim VAUGHT	
15:00	Storage of paraffin tissues: Increasing sample retrieval rates by automation Discussion	Berthold HUPPERTZ	
15:30	Quality assurance programs and tools to disseminate biobanking standards	Peter WATSON	
16:00	Implementing quality management in French Biobanks: Lessons from 10 years of experience	Myriam ZAOMI	
16:30	Towards a national cross-auditing system	Helmuth HASLACHER	
17:00	Internal and External Quality Control at the Integrated Biobank of Luxembourg	William MATHIESON	
17:30	Discussion		
18:00	End of meeting		

Attendance lists

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Tuesday May 17, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees A ▶ D 29

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <small>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanking infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanking and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</small>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ABBAS Houria	Centre hospitalier intercommunal de Créteil	houria.abbas@chicreteil.fr			X	X
ALYANAKIAN Marie-Alexandra	APHP	marie-alexandra.alyanikian@aphp.fr				
AMELIN Damien	Centre de Recherche en Myologie, UPMC / INSERM UMRS 974, CNRS FRE3617, AIM	damien.arnelin@courriel.upmc.fr			X	
Artaud-Botté Marie-Claire	GIE Neuro-CEB	marie-claire.artaud@neuroceb.org			X	X2 D x2
BARAU Caroline	Plateforme de Ressources	caroline.barau@aphp.fr			X	
BARRE Jérôme	CHIC Centre Hospitalier Intercommunal de Créteil	jerome.barre@chicreteil.fr				
BARTHELAIX Annick	CHU Angers	AnBarthelaix@chu-angers.fr				
BAUMGARTNER Florian	Karolinska Institutet SCILIFELAB - Suède	florian.baumgartner@scilifelab.se				

1/4

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <small>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanking infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanking and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</small>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
BEGAUD Evelyne	Institut Pasteur	evelyne.begaud@pasteur.fr			X	
BIOY Xavier	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	xavier.bioy@ut-capitole.fr			X	
Birwise Peyrottes Isabelle	Centre Antoine Lacassagne	isabelle.peyrottes@nic.univ-cancer.fr				
BLAIZOT Gaëtane	CHU Caen	blaizot-g@chu-caen.fr				
Blanché-Koch Héléne	Fondation Jean Dausset-CEPH	helene.blanche@cephb.fr			X	
BRIESEMEISTER Dana	ZebanC	dana.briesemeister@ceb.hiite.de			X	
BRISWALTER Jeanick	Université Nice Sophia Antipolis	Jeanick.Briswalter@unice.fr				
BUCCIARELLI Florence	CHU PURPAN	bucciarelli.f@chu-toulouse.fr			X	
BULLE Frédérique	BIOBANQUES	frederique.bulle@inserm.fr				
CABOUX Elodie	IARC	caboux@iarc.fr			X	
CERVO Silvia	CRO Aviano NCI	scervo@cro.it			X	
Chama SALMI	CryoStem	salmic@ipc-univcancer.fr				
CHAMI Antoine	BIOBANQUES					

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
CHAPATTE Laurence	Swiss biobanking platform	Laurence.chapatte@swissbiobanking.ch			X	D
CHASSANG Gauthier						D
CHESNE Christophe	BIOPREDIC INTERNATIO	christophe.chesne@biopredic.com				
CHINETTI Giulia	Université de Nice Sophia	giulia.chinetti@unice.fr			X	
CHOPIN Emilie	HCL - CBC Biotec	emilie.chopin01@chu-lyon.fr			X	D
CLAPISSON Gilles	Centre Léon Bérard	gilles.clapissou@lyon.unicancer.fr				
CLERMONT Dominique	Institut Pasteur	dominique.clermont@pasteur.fr				D
COGNET Céline	CHU BORDEAUX CRB plurithématique - Bordeaux Biothèques	celine.cognet@chu-bordeaux.fr			Y	
COLL Estelle	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis	coll@unice.fr				
COUSSENS Thibaut	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	thibaut.coussens@hotmail.fr			X	D
CRACIUN Ligia	Institut Jules Bordet	patricia.hoffman@bordet.be			X	D
CREPEL Mélanie	AP-HP Tumorothèque HUEP	emmanuel.roux@aphp.fr			X	D
CURRAT Christine	Swiss biobanking platform	Christine.currat@swissbiobanking.ch			X	D
DAVID Maha	BIOBANQUES	maha.david@inserm.fr				
DE JOUVENCEL Tiphaine	BIOBANQUES	tiphaine.dejouvence@inserm.fr				
DELEBEQUE Marie-Caroline	Tumorothèque Cochin	mariecaroline.delebecque@aphp.fr			X	D

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
DESCHILDRES Catherine	Inserm U1148					
DESILLE-DUGAST Mireille	CRB Santé - CHU de Rennes	Mireille.DESILLE-DUGAST@chu-rennes.fr			X	
DOLLE Laurent	BBMRI.BE	amandine.vercauteren@kankerregister.org			X	D
DOUCET Marika	BIOBANQUES - US13					N
Downing Jason	Illumina	jdowning@illumina.com				
DUFAY Nathalie	HCL-Neurobiotec	nathalie.dufay@chu-lyon.fr			X	D
DUPONT Carole	Brooks Automation	carole.dupont@brooks.com				
Cosmo philippe	CRB - ST-Etienne	Tumorothèque CRB - ST-Etienne			X	
Giorgio STAMATA	University of Trieste					D

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Tuesday May 17, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees E ▶ M

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ECHCHAKIR Hamid	BIOBANQUES	Hamid.echchakin@ins-ern.fr			X	
ECTORS Nadine	UZ - KULeuven	Nadine.Ectors@uzleuven.be			X	
EL KAIM Yves	CHRU de Montpellier	y-el_kaim@chu-montpellier.fr			X	
ERICSSON Ida	NTNU, HUNT biobank	ida.ericsson@ntnu.no			X	
ERKENSTAM Nina	Sahlgrenska biobank	nina.erkenstam@vgregion.se			X	D
ESCOFFIER CLEMENCE	HCL- CBC Biotec	clemence.escoffier@ctu-lyon.fr			X	D
ESLING Anne	INSERM US24 SFR NECKER CRB-ADN	anne.esling@inserm.fr			X	
FERNANDEZ David	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis					

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
GADRAS Coraline	CHU Tours	c.gadras@chu-tours.fr			X	
GELE Patrick	INSERM CIC1403- CRB	patrick.gele@univ-lille2.fr			X	D
GEORGE Fabienne	CHU UCL Namur	fabienne.george@uclouvain.be			X	D
GERNER Marlene	Medizinische Universität Wien	marlene.gerner@medunivien.ac.at				
GOFFLOT Stéphanie	Biothèque Hospitalo Universitaire de Liège	stephanie.gofflot@chu.ulg.ac.be			X	D
GORMALLY Emmanuelle	ESTBB - Université Catholique de Lyon	egormally@univ-catholyon.fr			X	D
GUTIERREZ-ROELENIS Ilse	Biothèque de l'Institut Roi Albert II	ilse.gutierrez@uclouvain.be			X	D
HADDAOUI Lamyia	FILOTHEQUE Institut Cochin	lamya.haddaoui@inserm.fr			X	D
HAMOUCHE Zakir	Eurobio	z.hamouche@eurobio.fr				
HARDY Isabelle	ESTBB	ihardy@univ-catholyon.fr				
HERPE Yves-Edouard	Biobanques Picardie	ye.herpe@biobanque-picardie.com			X	D
HISBERGUES Mikael	BIOBANQUES	michael.hisbergues@inserm.fr				
HURTADO-ORTIZ Raquel	Institut Pasteur	raquel.hurtado-ortiz@pasteur.fr			X	

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
JANAS Sylvie	Tumorothèque du C2RC Lille	sylvie.janas@chru-lille.fr				
JEZEQUEL Nathalie	CHU Brest	nathalie.jezequel@chu-brest.fr				
JOSEFSSON Agnetha	Sahlgrenska Biobank	agneta.m.josefsson@vgregion.se	<i>AJ</i>	<i>Agneta Josefsson</i>	X	
JRAD rhab	Faculté des sciences Nice	rnao.jrad1992@gmail.com	<i>RJR</i>	<i>Rhab</i>		
KUZBARI Suzanne	Département de Génétique- UF de Génétique Moléculaire	suzanne.kuzbari@aphp.fr	<i>Suzanne</i>	<i>Suzanne</i>	X	
KYNAST Katharina	NCT TISSUE BANK Pathologisches Institut Ulmerstr. 63a D-69115 Heidelberg	katharina.kynast@med.uni-heidelberg.de	<i>K. Kynast</i>	<i>K. Kynast</i>	X	
LARGEAU Marine	HEGP - Centre de ressources biologiques et tumorothèque	marine.largeau@aphp.fr	<i>Marine</i>	<i>Marine</i>	X	
LE MEUR Sébastien	CRB Santé Brest	sebastien.lemeur@chu-brest.fr	<i>Sébastien</i>	<i>Sébastien</i>	X	
LEROY Céline	INSERM CIC1433	c.eroy@chru-nancy.fr	<i>C. Leroy</i>	<i>C. Leroy</i>	X	
LESUEUR Fabienne	Inserm U900	fabienne.lesueur@curie.fr	<i>Fabienne</i>	<i>Fabienne</i>	X	
LOMAZZI Sandra	CRB LORRAIN - CHRU NANCY	s.lomazzi@chru-nancy.fr	<i>Sandra</i>	<i>Sandra</i>	X	
LORIMIER PHILIPPE	CENTRE DE RESSOURCES BIOLOGIQUES CHU	plorimier@chu-granoble.fr	<i>Philippe</i>	<i>Philippe</i>	X	
MALLET David	DRCI CHU NICE	mallet.d@chu-nice.fr	<i>David</i>	<i>David</i>		
MALSERVET Nicolas	BIOBANQUES	nicolas.malservet@inserm.fr	<i>Nicolas</i>	<i>Nicolas</i>		
Malzac Aurelie	Institut Paoli Calmettes	malzac@ipc.unicancer.fr	<i>Aurélien</i>	<i>Aurélien</i>	X	
Manivet Philippe	CRB-LRB	philippe.manivet@aphp.fr	<i>Philippe</i>	<i>Philippe</i>	X	

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
MARIANI Odette	INSTITUT CURIE	odette.mariani@curie.fr	<i>Odette</i>	<i>Odette</i>	X	
MAROT Gérard	IRELEC	irelec@irelec-alcen.com	<i>Gérard</i>	<i>Gérard</i>	X	
MEINUNG Bettina	German Biobank Node (GBN)	meinung@qpra.de	<i>Bettina</i>	<i>Bettina</i>	X	
MEKONG ADIOGO Elizabeth	BIOBANQUES	elizabeth.mekongadiogo@inserm.fr	<i>Elizabeth</i>	<i>Elizabeth</i>		
MONTAGNE-STORA Samantha	INSTITUT JEROME LEJEUNE	celine.du.boispean@institutjeune.org	<i>Samantha</i>	<i>Samantha</i>	X	
MONTERRAT Torá	FIMM	mtora@mim.es	<i>Torá</i>	<i>Torá</i>	X	
MUTTAQI Ubaida	BIOBANQUES	ubaida.muttaqi@inserm.fr	<i>Ubaida</i>	<i>Ubaida</i>		X
GUO Yongli	China		<i>Yongli Guo</i>	<i>Yongli Guo</i>	X	
KREMER Andreas	IITM Solutions	andreas.kremer@iitm-solutions.com	<i>Andreas</i>	<i>Andreas</i>		X
FAYE Pierre-Alexandre	ICM Val d'Aurelle	pierre-alexandre.faye@paul.fr	<i>Pierre-Alexandre</i>	<i>Pierre-Alexandre</i>	X	
GEILNER Monika	Medical University Vienna	monika.geilner@meduniwien.ac.at	<i>Monika</i>	<i>Monika</i>	X	
HASLACHER Adeline	Hedler Viennese	adeline.haslacher@hedler.com	<i>Adeline</i>	<i>Adeline</i>	X	
Hollmann, Susanna	Uni Zoloto	shollman@uni-zoloto.ru	<i>Susanna</i>	<i>Susanna</i>		X
GERLIER Denis	CIRI Lyon		<i>Denis</i>	<i>Denis</i>		X
WUPPERTZ Beatrix		beatrix.wuppertz@med.uni-wuerzburg.de	<i>Beatrix</i>	<i>Beatrix</i>	X	
LE CORRE Fabrice			<i>Fabrice</i>	<i>Fabrice</i>	X	

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 676550.

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Tuesday May 17, 2016
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Attendance Sheet - Attendees N ▶ Z

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE	
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
D NASRI Saviz	CRB Tumorothèque CHU de Reims	snasri@chu-reims.fr			X
R NENUTIL Rudolf	Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute	nenuiti@mou.cz			
ONOGORO OBRUCHE	UTM DREDGING LTD	sttorneys@alexscottlawoffice.com			
B ORTEGA-PAIND Eva	Lund University Dpt of Immunotechnology	eva.ortega-paino@immun.lth.se			X
Ozgul Yusuf	Erciyes University	ozcans@erciyes.edu.tr			✓
Pace Nikolai	University of Malta	nikolai.p.pace@um.edu.mt			
D PARDOUX Guillemette	BIOBANQUES	guillemette.pardoux@inserm.fr			

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
D PASTERK Markus	BBMRI-ERIC	admin.dir@bbmri-eric.eu			X
PERKMANN Thomas	Medizinische Universität Wien	thomas.perkmann@meduniwien.ac.at			
D PERLAZA Blanca Liliana	Plate-forme CARTAs du Centre de Recherche Translationnel (Investigation Clinique et)	blanca-liliana.perlaiza@pasteur.fr			
PIERRE-ARNAUD Faye	ICM-CRB	pierrearnaud.faye@gmail.com			
D PIGEON Anna	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	anna.pigeon@live.fr			✓
PIROT Nelly	INSERM U1194	nelly.pirot@inserm.fr			
Poirot-Mazères isabelle	université Toulouse 1 capitole	isabelle.poirot-mazeres@ut-capitole.fr			✓
D POLIZZI ANSELMO Annalisa	CRO Aviano NCI	a.polizzianselmo@libero.it			X
D POUHYET Claire	BIOBANQUES	claire.pouhyet@inserm.fr			
RAMON Olivier	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis				
RENAUD Florence	CHRU Lille	florence.renaud@chru-lille.fr			
RIAL SEBBAG Emmanuelle	BIOBANQUES				

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
D Ruckebauer Christine	University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna	christine.ruckebauer@vetmeduni.ac.at				
Rufenach Cornelia	Charité- German Biobank Node BBMRI.de	cornelia.rufenach@charite.de				
D SCHMITT Sabrina	Tissue Bank of the NCT, Heidelberg University Hospital	Sabrina.schmitt@med.uni-heidelberg.de			X	
D SERVAIS Marie-Dominique	Institut de Recherches Internationales SERVIER	marie-dominique.servais@servier.com			X	
D SIYOUCEF Souhila	PremUp	sivoucef.safia@gmail.com			X	
D SOBRIER Marie-Laure	BIOBANQUES	marie-laure.sobrier@inserm.fr				
D SONG Yutong	Shanghai Clinical Research Center	yutong.song@scrcnet.org				
D SOUDJAY Djamilia	BIOBANQUES	djamilia.soudjay@inserm.fr				
TISSOT Lucie	CHRU BESANCON	l.tissot@chu-besancon.fr				
VASSEUR Stéphane	Myobank Institut de Myologie	s.vasseur@institut-myologie.org			X	
VIARD Patricia	CHU de Rennes	patricia.VIARD@chu-rennes.fr			X	
VIVIEN Denis	CHU Caen	vivien@cyceron.fr				
D Walter Ingrid	University of Veterinary Medicine	ingrid.walter@vetmeduni.ac.at				
D Wieser Monika	University of Veterinary Medicine	monika.wieser@vetmeduni.ac.at			X	

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
Wutte Andrea	BBMRI-ERIC	andrea.wutte@bbmri-eric.eu				
YANNING Cai	Capital Medical University de Pékin		Abs.			
YONGLI Guo	Capital Medical University de Pékin		Abs.			
Salmi Chama	Cryosystem	salmichama@gmail.com			Y	D
N. TORÀ, Montserrat	ISS IIMM	mtora@iimm.es			Y	
D STUMPTNER Cornelia	BBMRI.at	cornelia.stumptner@med.uni-graz.at			Y	

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606700
MONTSERRAT
TORÀ
Cornelia Stumptner @
meduni-graz.at

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Tuesday May 17, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Sponsor

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE	
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
DIDIERJEAN Olivier	AFFYMETRIX	Olivier_Didierjean@affymetrix.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Non	
KELLNREITER Niklas	AFFYMETRIX	Niklas_Kellnreiter@affymetrix.com	Ne viendra pas -		
TEYSSIER Franck	AFFYMETRIX	Franck_Teyssier@affymetrix.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
LEGUILLON Bernard	FROILABO	b.leguillon@froilabo.com	Ne viendra pas		
REBMANN Julien	FROILABO	j.rebmann@froilabo.com			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> oui
MAHJOUB Walid	FROILABO	w.mahjoub@froilabo.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> oui	
DOMENJOZ Cyril	GRIENER BIOONE	Cyril.Domenjoz@gbo.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Non	
DOWING Jason	Illumina	jdowning@illumina.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> oui	

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE	
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
VACHER Coralie	Illumina	cvacher@illumina.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> oui	
de MONTALIER Axel	MODUL BIO	a.demontalier@modulbio.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Hugo BAYLE	MODUL BIO	h.bayle@modulbio.com			
JACOTOT Laurent	MODUL BIO	l.jacotot@modulbio.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
de JONG Mark	PROTEIGENE	mark.jong@fluidx.eu			
DUPONT Carole	PROTEIGENE	Carole.Dupont@brooks.com			
GEMONET Jonathan	PROTEIGENE	gemonet@proteigene.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Non	
OMASSON Alain	PROTEIGENE	omasson@proteigene.com	Non		
KROME Jürgen	SYSMEX	Krome.Juergen@sysmex-europe.com		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> oui	
BARTHELEMY-BLANC Rémi	TECHNIDATA	remi.barthelemy-blanc@techndata-web.com			
CHEYNET Stéphane	TECHNIDATA	stephane.cheynet@techndata-web.com			

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Tuesday May 17, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Intervenants

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE	
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
D BECKER Karl-Friedrich	Universität München- Institut für pathologie	kf.becker@tum.de			
Bjorkmann Jens	TATAA Biocenter - Göteborg	Jens.bjorkman@tataa.com			
BONNET Jacques	Bordeaux University	bonnet@image.eu			
D CLEMENT Bruno	BIOBANQUES - INSERM CRBs Foie Rennes	bruno.clement@inserm.fr			
DAGHER Georges	BIOBANQUES - INSERM	georges.dagher@inserm.fr			
D DAIDONE Maria Grazia	Istituto Tumori, Milan, Italy	MariaGrazia.Daidone@istitutotumori.mi.it			
DUYCKAERTS Charles	ICM	charles.duyckaerts@stlaph.fr			

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Avec photo
Pratic
Image

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE	
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
ERB Gilles	Roche diagnostics, France	gilles.erb@roche.com			
CERLIER Denis	CIRI Lyon	denis.gerlier@inserm.fr			
D Halascher Helmut	Medizinische Universität Wien	helmuth.haslacher@meduniwien.ac.at			✓
D HOFMAN Paul	CHU Nice	HOFMAN.P@chu-nice.fr			
D HÖLLMAN Suzanne	Universität Potsdam	shollman@uni-potsdam.de			
HUPPETZ Berthold	Medical University of Graz, Austria	biobank@medunigraz.at			
JUNOT Christophe	MetahubCEA, Paris	Christophe.JUNOT@cea.fr			
KREMER Andreas	Ittm Solutions	andreas.kremer@ittm-solutions.com			
LAVITRANO Maria-Luisa	BBMRI.it	marialuisa.lavitrano@unimb.it			x
LAWLOR Rita T.	ARC - University of Verona-Italy	rita.lawlor@arc-net.it			
D LITTON Jan Eric	BBMRI	secretary@bbmri-eric.eu			

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BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Wednesday May 18, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees A ▶ D

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ABBAS Houria	Centre hospitalier intercommunal	houria.abbas@chicreteil.fr				
ALYANAKIAN Marie-Alexandra	APHP	marie-alexandra.alyanakian@aphp.fr				
AMELIN Damien	Centre de Recherche en Myologie, UPMC / INSERM UMRS 974, CNRS FRE3617, AIM	damien.amelin@courmel.upmc.fr		X		
Artaud-Botté Marie-Claire	GIE Neuro-CEB	marie-claire.artaud@neuroceb.org				
BARAU Caroline	Plateforme de Ressources	caroline.barau@aphp.fr			X	
BARRE Jérôme	CHIC Centre Hospitalier Intercommunal de Créteil	jerome.barre@chicreteil.fr				
BARTHELAIX Annick	CHU Angers	AnBarthelax@chu-angers.fr			X	
BAUMGARTNER Florian	Karolinska Institutet SCILIFELAB - Suède	florian.baumgartner@scilifelab.se				

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
BEGAUD Evelyne	institut Pasteur	evelyne.begaud@pasteur.fr				
BIOY Xavier	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	xavier.bioy@ut-capitole.fr				
Birtwisle Peyrottes Isabelle	Centre Antoine Lacassagne	isabelle.peyrottes@nic.unicancer.fr				
BLAIZOT Gaetane	CHU Caen	blaizot-g@chu-caen.fr		X		
Blanché-Koch Héliène	Fondation Jean Dausset-CEPH	helene.blanche@cephb.fr		X		
BRIESEMEISTER Dana	ZeBanC	dana.briesemeister@charite.de				
BRISSWALTER Jeanick	Université Nice Sophia Antipolis	Jeanick.Brisswalter@unice.fr				
BUCCIARELLI Florence	CHU PURPAN	bucciarelli.f@chu-toulouse.fr		X		
BULLE Frédérique	BIOBANQUES	frederique.bulle@inserm.fr				
CABOUX Elodie	IARC	caboux@iarc.fr		X		
CERVO Silvia	CRO Aviano NCI	scervo@cro.it				
Chama SALMI	CryoStem	salmic@ipc-unicancer.fr				
CHAMI Antoine	BIOBANQUES					

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 676550.

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
CHAPATTE Laurence	Swiss biobanking platform	Laurence.chapatte@swissbiobanking.ch				
CHASSANG Gauthier						
CHESNE Christophe	BIOPREDIC INTERNATIO	christophe.chesne@biopredic.com				
CHINETTI Giulia	Université de Nice Sophia	giulia.chinetti@unice.fr				
CHOPIN Emilie	HCL - CBC Biotec	emilie.chopin01@chu-lyon.fr			X	
CLAPISSON Gilles	Centre Léon Bérard	gilles.clapisson@yon.unicancer.fr				
CLERMONT Dominique	Institut Pasteur	dominique.clermont@pasteur.fr				
COGNET Céline	CHU BORDEAUX CRB plurithématique - Bordeaux Biothèques	celine.cognet@chu-bordeaux.fr			Y	
COLL Estelle	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis	coll@unice.fr				
COUSSENS Thibaut	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	thibaut.coussens@hotmail.fr				
CRACIUN Ligia	Institut Jules Bordet	patricia.hoffman@bordet.be			Y	
CREPEL Mélanie	AP-HP Tumorothèque HUEP	emmanuel.roux@aphp.fr			Y	
CURRAT Christine	Swiss biobanking platform	Christine.currat@swissbiobanking.ch				
DAVID Maha	BIOBANQUES	maha.david@inserm.fr				
DE JOUVENCEL Tiphaine	BIOBANQUES	tiphaine.dejouvencel@inserm.fr				
DELEBECQUE Marie-Caroline	Tumorothèque Cochin	mariecaroline.delebecque@aphp.fr			X	

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pas de "s" → attention à modifier

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
DESCHILDRES Catherine	Inserm U1148					
DESILLE-DUGAST Mireille	CRB Santé - CHU de Rennes	Mireille.DESILLE-DUGAST@chu-rennes.fr				
DOLLE Laurent	BBMRI.BE	amandine.vercauteren@kanregister.org			Y	
DOUCET Marika	BIOBANQUES - US13					
Downing Jason	Illumina	jdowning@illumina.com				
DUFAY Nathalie	HCL-Neurobiotec	nathalie.dufay@chu-lyon.fr			X	
DUPONT Carole	Brooks Automation	carole.dupont@brooks.com				
Cosmo Philippe	CRB Tumorothèque					
STANTA Giulia	Université of Piemonte					

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 676550.

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Wednesday May 18 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees E ▶ M

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ECHCHAKIR Hamid	BIOBANQUES	Hamid.echchakir@insERM.fr		Y		
ECTORS Nadine	UZ - KULeuven	Nadine.Ectors@uzleuven.be				
EL KAIM Yves	CHRU de Montpellier	y-el_kaim@chu-montpellier.fr		X		
ERICSSON Ida	NTNU, HUNT biobank	ida.ericsson@ntnu.no		Y		
ERKENSTAM Nina	Sahlgrenska biobank	nina.erkenstam@vgregion.se				
ESCOFFIER CLEMENCE	HCL - CBC Biotec	clémence.escoffier@chuliyon.fr		X		
ESLING Anne	INSERM US24 SFR NECKER CRB-ADN	anne.esling@inserm.fr		X		

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
FERNANDEZ David	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis					
GADRAS Coraline	CHU Tours	c.gadras@chu-tours.fr		X		
GELE Patrick	INSERM CIC1403- CRB	patrick.gele@univ-lille2.fr		X		
GEORGE Fabienne	CHU UCL Namur	fabienne.george@uclouvain.be		Y		
GERNER Marlene	Medizinische Universität Wien	marlene.gerner@medunivwien.ac.at				
GOFFLOT Stéphanie	Biothèque Hospitalo Universitaire de Liège	stephanie.gofflot@chulig.ac.be		X		
GORMALLY Emmanuelle	ESTBB - Université Catholique de Lyon	egormally@univ-catholyon.fr		X		
GUTIERREZ-ROELENIS Ilse	Biothèque de l'Institut Roi Albert II	ilse.gutierrez@ucloouvain.be		X		
HADDAOUI Lamya	FILOTHEQUE Institut Cochin	lamya.haddaoui@inserm.fr				
HAMOUCHE Zakir	Eurobio	z.hamouche@eurobio.fr				
HARDY Isabelle	ESTBB	ihardy@univ-catholyon.fr				
HERPE Yves-Edouard	Biobanques Picardie	yves.herpe@biobanque-picardie.com		X		

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE	
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
HISBERGUES Mikael	BIOBANQUES	michael.hisbergues@neerm.fr			
HURTADO-ORTIZ Raquel	Institut Pasteur	raquel.hurtado-ortiz@pasteur.fr			
JANAS Sylvie	Tumorothèque du C2RC Lille	sylvie.janas@chru-lille.fr			
JEZEQUEL Nathalie	CHU Brest	nathalie.jezequel@chubrest.fr			
JOSEFSSON Agnetha	Sahlgrenska Biobank	agneta.m.josefsson@vgregion.se			
JRAD rhab	Faculté des sciences Nice	rhab.jrad1992@gmail.com			
KUZZARI Suzanne	Département de Génétique-UF de Génétique Moléculaire NCI / ISSUS Bank	suzanne.kuzbari@aphp.fr			X
KYNAST Katharina	Pathologisches Institut Universität Heidelberg	katharina.kynast@med.uni-heidelberg.de			X
LARGEAU Martine	HECR - Centre de ressourcesbiologique et tumorothèque	martine.largeau@aphp.fr			X
LE MEUR Sébastien	CRB Santé Brest	sebastien.lemeur@chubrest.fr			X
LEROY Céline	INSERM QC1433	c.eroy@chru-nancy.fr			X
LESUEUR Fabienne	Inserm U900	fabienne.lesueur@curie.fr			X
LÓMAZZI Sarah	CHU LORRAINE - CHRU NANCY	s.lomazzi@chru-nancy.fr			X
LORMIER PHILIPPE	CENTRE DE RESSOURCES BIOLOGIQUES CHU DRCI	plormier@chugrenoble.fr			X
MALLET David	CHU NICE	mallet.d@chu-nice.fr			

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE	
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N
MALSERVET Nicolas	BIOBANQUES	nicolas.malservet@inserm.fr			
Matzac Aurelie	Institut Paoli Calmettes	matzaca@ipc.unicancr.fr			X
Manivet Philippe	CRB-LRB	philippe.manivet@aphp.fr			
MARIANI Odette	INSTITUT CURIE	odette.mariani@curie.fr			X
MAROT Gérard	IRELEC	irelec@irelec-alcen.com			
MEINUNG Bettina	German Biobank Node (GBN)	meinung@bpra.de			X
MEKONG ADIOGO Elizabeth	BIOBANQUES	elizabeth.mekong-adiogo@inserm.fr			
MONTAGNE-STORA Samantha	INSTITUT JEROME LEJEUNE	samanta.du.boispean@institutlejeune.org			
MONTERRAT Tori	FIMM	mtora@imim.es			X
MUTTAQI Ubaida	BIOBANQUES	ubaida.muttaqi@inserm.fr			
FAYE Perrine Anouk	ICM de Bordeaux	perrine.faye@icm-bordeaux.fr			
LOIBNER Mathias	Medical University Graz	mathias.loibner@meduni-graz.at			X
GUO Yongli	China				
KREMER Andreia	ITTM solution				
GERNER Maleno	Madagascar University	maleno.gerner@univ-madagascar.mg			X

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BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING

Wednesday May 18, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees N ▶ Z

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
NAŠRI Šaviz	CRB Tumorošké CHU de Reims	snasri@chu-reims.fr		X		
NENUTIL Rudolf	Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute	nenutl@mou.cz				
ONOGORO OBRUCHE	UTM DREDGING LTD	allorneys@alexscottlawoffi ce.com				
ORTEGA-PAINO Eva	Lund University Dpt of Immunotechnology	eva.ortega-paino@immun.lth.se				
Özkal Yusuf	Erciyes University	ozkans@erciyes.edu.tr				
Pace Nikolai	University of Malta	nikolai.p.pace@um.edu.mt				
PARDOUX Guillemette	BIOBANQUES	guillemette.pardoux@inser m.fr				

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
PASTERK Markus	BBMRI-ERIC	admin.dr@bbmri-eric.eu				
PERKMANN Thomas	Medizinische Universität Wien	thomas.perkmann@medu niwien.ac.at				
PERLAZA Bianca Liliana	PI3S-NORME ICARES du Centre de Recherche Translationnel Investigation Clinique et	blanca-liliana.perlaza@pasteur.fr				
PIERRE-ARNAUD Faye	ICM-CRB	pierrearnaud.faye@gmail.c om				
PIGEON Anna	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	anna.pigeon@live.fr				
PIROT Nelly	INSERM U1194	nelly.piro@inserm.fr				
Poirot-Mazères Isabelle	université Toulouse 1 capitale	isabelle.poirot-mazeres@ut-capitole.fr				
POLIZZI ANSELMO Annalisa	CRO Aviano NCI	a.polizianselmo@libero.it				
POUHYET Claire	BIOBANQUES	claire.pouhyet@inserm.fr				
RAMON Olivier	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis					
RENAUD Florence	CHRU Lille	florance.renaud@chru- lille.fr				
RIAL SEBBAG Emmanuelle	BIOBANQUES					

2/3

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
Ruckbauer Christine	University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna	christine.ruckbauer@vetmeduni.ac.at				
Rufenerach Cornelia	Charité- German Biobank Node BBMRI.de	cornelia.rufenerach@charite.de				
SCHMITT Sabrina	Tissue Bank of the NCT, Heidelberg University Hospital	Sabrina.schmitt@med.uni-heidelberg.de		X		
SERVAIS Marie-Dominique	Institut de Recherches Internationales SERVIER	marie.dominique.servais@servier.com				
SIYOUCEF Southia	PremUp	siyoucefsafa@gmail.com			X	
SOBRIER Marie-Laure	BIOBANQUES	marie-laure.sobrier@inserm.fr				
SONG Yutong	Shanghai Clinical Research Center	yutong.song@scrcn.net.org				
SOUDJAY Djamilia	BIOBANQUES	djamilia.soudjay@inserm.fr				
TISSOT Lucie	CHRU BESANCON	l.tissot@chu-besancon.fr				
VASSEUR Stephane	Myobank Institut de Myologie	s.vasseur@institut-myologie.org				
VIARD Patricia	CHU de Rennes	patricia.VIARD@chu-rennes.fr				
VIVIEN Denis	CHU Caen	vivien@cyceron.fr				
Walter Ingrid	University of Veterinary Medicine	ingrid.walter@vetmeduni.ac.at			X	
Wieser Monika	University of Veterinary Medicine	monika.wieser@vetmeduni.ac.at		X		

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
Wutte Andrea	BBMRI-ERIC	andrea.wutte@bbmri-eric.eu		X		
YANNING Cai	Capital Medical University de Pékin					
YONGLI Guo	Capital Medical University de Pékin			X		
SALMI Océane	CROSTON	oceanesalmi@croston.com		Y		
STUMPFER Cornelia	BBMRI at			X		

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BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Wednesday May 18, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Intervenants

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
BECKER Karl Friedrich	Universität München-Institut für pathologie	kf.becker@tum.de	x			
BJORKMANN Jens	TATAA Biocenter - Göteborg	Jens.bjorkman@tataa.com	envoyé par poste (Georges, Claire)			
BONNET Jacques	Bordeaux University	bonnet@imagene.eu				
CLEMENT Bruno	BIOBANQUES - INSERM-CRBs Foie Rennes	bruno.clement@inserm.fr				
DAGHER Georges	BIOBANQUES - INSERM	georges.dagher@inserm.fr	x			
DAIDONE Maria Grazia	Istituto Tumori, Milan, Italy	MariaGrazia.Daidone@istitutotumori.mi.it	x			
DUYCKAERTS Charles	ICM	charles.duyckaerts@p.sl.aqho.fr				

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ERB Gilles	Roche diagnostics, France	gilles.erb@roche.com				
GERLIER Denis	CIRI Lyon	denis.gerlier@inserm.fr				
HASLACHER Helmut HASLACHER Helmut	Medizinische Universität Wien	helmuth.haslacher@meduniwien.ac.at				
HOFMAN Paul	CHU Nice	HOFMAN P@chu-nice.fr				
HÖLLMAN Suzanne	Universität Potsdam	shollman@uni-potsdam.de				
HUPPETZ Berthold	Medical University of Graz, Austria	biobank@medunigraz.at				
JUNOT Christophe	MetahubCEA, Paris	Christophe_JUNOT@cea.fr				
KREMER Andreas	Ittm Solutions	andreas.kremer@ittm-solutions.com				
LAVITRANO Maria-Luisa	BBMRI.it	marialuisa.lavitrano@unimib.it				
LAWLOR Rita T.	ARC - University of Verona-Italy	rita.lawlor@arc-net.it				
LITTON Jan Eric	BBMRI	secretary@bbmri-eric.eu				

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
LOIBNER Martina	Medical University of Graz, Austria	martina.loibner@medunigraz.at				
LUNDEBERG Joakim	Karolinska Institute - Sweden	joakim.lundeberg@scilifeab.se				
MATHIESON William	Ibbl.lu	William.Mathieson@ibbl.lu				
METSPALIJ Andres	Estonian Genome Center	andres.metspalu@ut.ee	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
MOORE Helen	NIH Biorepositories and Biospecimen Research Branch	moorehe@mail.nih.gov				
MORENTE Manuel	UNIO - Biobank unit of the Spanish national cancer centre	mmorente@orio.es				
NAIMI Ben Youssef	Anygenes, Paris	ben.naimi@anygenes.com	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
OELMUELLER Uwe	QIAGEN	uwe.oelmueeller@qiagen.com				
OLLIER Bill	Manchester University Centre for integrated genomic Medical	Bill.Ollier@manchester.ac.uk				
PARODI Barbara	BBMRI.it - Banca Biologica e Cell Factory	barbara.parodi@hsanmartino.it	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
RUAN Liangliang	SCRC - Shanghai Clinical Research center	liangliang.ruan@scriet.org				
STANTA Giorgio	Università di Trieste, IT	stanta@impactsnetwork.eu stanta@units.it	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
TURANO Paola	University of Florence	turano@cern.unifi.it				
VACHER Coralie	Cambridge Regulatory Services	cvacher@illumina.com	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
VAUGHT Jim	ISBER	javaugh44@gmail.com				
WANG Peng		wangpeng@comu.edu.cn				
WATSON Peter	BC Cancer Agency, Vancouver Island Center	pwatson@bccancer.bc.ca				
WICHMANN Erich	Institute of Epidemiology at the Helmholtz Center Munich	wichmann@helmholtz-muenchen.de	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
YUILLE Martin		martin.yuille@manchester.ac.uk				
ZAOMI Myriam	BIOBANQUES	myriam.zaomi@inserm.fr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
ZATLOUKAL Kurt	BBMRI.at	kurt.zatloukal@medunigraz.at				

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BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING

Wednesday May 18, 2016

Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Sponsor

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
DIDIERJEAN Olivier	AFFYMETRIX	Olivier_Didierjean@affymetrix.com				
KELLNREITER Niklas	AFFYMETRIX	Niklas_Kellnreiter@affymetrix.com				
TEYSSIER Franck	AFFYMETRIX	Franck_Teyssier@affymetrix.com				
LEGUILLON Bernard	FRÖILABO	bleguillon@froilabo.com				
REBMANN Julien	FRÖILABO	j_rebmann@froilabo.com				X
MAHJOUB Walid	FRÖILABO	w.mahjoub@froilabo.com				X
DOMENJOZ Cyril	GRIENER BIOONE	Cyril.Domenjoz@gbo.com				X
DOWING Jason	Illumina	jdowning@illumina.com				X

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
VACHER Coralie	Illumina	cvacher@illumina.com				
de MONTALIER Axel	MODUL BIO	a.demontalier@modul-bio.com				X
HUGO BAYLE	MODUL BIO	h.bayle@modul-bio.com				
JACOTOT Laurent	MODUL BIO	l.jacotot@modul-bio.com				
de JONG Mark	PROTEIGENE	mark.jong@fluidx.eu				
DUPONT Carole	PROTEIGENE	Carole.Dupont@brook-s.com				N
GEMONET Jonathan	PROTEIGENE	gemonet@proteigene.com				Y
OMASSON Alain	PROTEIGENE	omasson@proteigene.com	NON			
KROME Jürgen	SYSMEX	Krome.Juergen@sysmex-europe.com				
BARTHELEMY-BLANC Rémi	TECHNIDATA	remi.caron@remy-blanc@technidata-web.com				
CHEYNET Stéphane	TECHNIDATA	stephane.cheynet@technidata-web.com				

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BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Thursday May 19, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees A ▶ D

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ABBAS Houria	Centre hospitalier Intercom	houria.abbas@chcitreteil.fr				
ALYANAKIAN Marie-Alexandra	APHP	marie-alexandra.alyanakian@aphp.fr				
AMELIN Damien	Centre de Recherche en Myologie, UPMC / INSERM UMRS 974, CNRS ERE3617_AIM	damien.amelin@courmel.upmc.fr			X	
Artaud-Botté Marie-Claire	GIE Neuro-CEB	marie-claire.artaud@neurocebt.org			X	
BARAU Caroline	Plateforme de Ressources	caroline.barau@aphp.fr				
BARRE Jérôme	CHIC Centre Hospitalier Intercommunal de Crétail	jerome.barre@chicretail.fr				
BARTHELAIX Annick	CHU Angers	AnBarthelaix@chu-angers.fr				
BAUMGARTNER Florian	Karolinska Institutet SCILIFELAB - Suède	florian.baumgartner@scilifelab.se				

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
BEGAUD Evelyne	Institut Pasteur	evelyne.begaud@pasteur.fr				
BIOY Xavier	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	xavier.bioy@ut-capitole.fr				
Birtwisle Peyrottes Isabelle	Centre Antoine Lacassagne	isabelle.peyrottes@nic.unicancer.fr			X	
BLAIZOT Gaetane	CHU Caen	blaizot-g@chu-caen.fr				
Bianché-Koch Héléne	Fondation Jean Dausset-CEPH	helene.blanche@cephb.fr			X	
BRIESEMEISTER Dana	ZeBarC	dana.brissmeister@baric.de			X	
BRISSWALTER Jeanick	Université Nice Sophia Antipolis	Jeanick.Brisswalter@unica.fr				
BUCCIARELLI Florence	CHU PURPAN	bucciarelli.f@chu-toulouse.fr			X	
BULLE Frédérique	BIOBANQUES	frederique.bulle@inserm.fr				
CABOUX Elodie	IARC	caboux@iarc.fr			X	
CERVO Silvia	CRO Aviano NCI	scervo@cro.it			X	
Chama SALMI	CryoStem	salmic@ipc-unicancer.fr			Y	
CHAMI Antoine	BIOBANQUES					

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
CHAPATTE Laurence	Swiss biobanking platform	Laurence.chapatte@swissbiobanking.ch		X		
CHASSANG Gauthier						
CHESNE Christophe	BIOPREDIC INTERNATIONAL	christophe.chesne@biopredic.com				
CHINETTI Giulia	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis	giulia.chinetti@unice.fr				
CHOPIN Emilie	HCL - CBC Biotec	emilie.chopin01@chu-lyon.fr		X		
CLAPISSON Gilles	Centre Léon Bérard	gilles.clapissou@lyon.unicancer.fr				
CLERMONT Dominique	Institut Pasteur	dominique.clermont@pasteur.fr				
COGNET Céline	CHU BORDEAUX CRB plurithématique - Bordeaux Biobanques	celine.cognet@chu-bordeaux.fr				
COLL Estelle	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis	coll@unice.fr				
COUSSENS Thibaut	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	thibaut.coussens@hotmail.fr				
CRACIUN Ligia	Institut Jules Bordet	patricia.hoffman@bordet.be		X		
CREPEL Mélanie	AP-HP Tumorothèque HUEP	emmanuel.roux@aphp.fr				
CURRAT Christine	Swiss biobanking platform	Christine.currat@swissbiobanking.ch		X		
DAVID Maha	BIOBANQUES	maha.david@inserm.fr				
DE JOUVENCEL Tiphaine	BIOBANQUES	tiphaine.de-jouvencel@inserm.fr				
DELEBECQUE Marie-Caroline	Tumorothèque Cochin	mariecaroline.delebecque@aphp.fr		X		

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
DESCHILDRES Catherine	Inserm U1148					
DESILLE-DUGAST Mireille	CRB Santé - CHU de Rennes	mireille.desille-dugast@chu-rennes.fr		X		
IDOLLE Laurent	BBMRI.BE	amandine.vercauteren@kankerregister.org				
DOUCET Marika	BIOBANQUES - US13					
Downing Jason	illumina	jdowning@illumina.com				
DUFAY Nathalie	HCL-Neurobiotec	nathalie.dufay@chu-lyon.fr				
DUPONT Carole	Brooks Automation	carole.dupont@brooks.com				

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Thursday May 19 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees E ▶ M

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanking infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanking and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ECHCHAKIR Hamid	BIOBANQUES	Hamid.echchakir@insrm.fr		Y		
ECTORS Nadine	UZ - KULeuven	Nadine.Ectors@uzleuven.be				
EL KAIM Yves	CHRU de Montpellier	y-el_kaim@chu-montpellier.fr				
ERICSSON Ida	NTNU, HUNT biobank	ida.ericsson@ntnu.no		X		
ERKENSTAM Nina	Sahlgrenska biobank	nina.erkenstam@vgre.glon.se				
ESCOFFIER CLEMENCE	HCL - CBC Biotec	clemence.escoffier@chu-lyon.fr		X		
ESLING Anne	INSERM US24 SFR NECKER CRB-ADN	anne.esling@inserm.fr		X		

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
FERNANDEZ David	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis					
GADRAS Coraline	CHU Tours	c.gadras@chu-tours.fr		X		
GELE Patrick	INSERM CIC1403- CRB	patrick.gele@univ-lille2.fr		X		
GEORGE Fabienne	CHU UCL Namur	fabienne.george@uclouvain.be		X	*	
GERNER Marlene	Medizinische Universität Wien	marlene.gerner@med.uniwien.ac.at		X		
GOFFLOT Stéphanie	Biothèque Hospitalo Universitaire de Liège	stephanie.gofflot@chu.ucl.ac.be		X	*	
GORMALLY Emmanuelle	ESTBB - Université Catholique de Lyon	egormally@univ-catholyon.fr		X		
GUTIERREZ-ROELENS Ilse	Biothèque de l'Institut Roi Albert II	ilse.gutierrez@udouva.in.be		X	*	
HADDAOUI Lamyia	FILOTHEQUE Institut Cochin	lamya.haddaoui@inserm.fr				
HAMOUCHE Zakir	Eurobio	z.hamouche@eurobio.fr				
HARDY Isabelle	ESTBB	ihardy@univ-catholyon.fr				
HERPE Yves-Edouard	Biobanques Picardie	ye.herpe@biobanque-picardie.com				

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NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
				Y	N	
HISBERGUES Mikael	BIOBANQUES	michael.hisbergues@nsem.fr			X	
HURTADO-ORTIZ Raquel	Institut Pasteur	raquel.hurtado-ortiz@pasteur.fr			X	
JANAS Sylvie	Tumorothèque du C2RC Lille	sylvie.janas@chru-lille.fr			X	
JEZEQUEL Nathalie	CHU Brest	nathalie.jezequel@chu-brest.fr				
JOSEFSSON Agnetha	Sahlgrenska Biobank	agneta.m.josefsson@vregion.se				
JRAD rihab	Faculté des sciences Nice	rihab.jrad1992@gmail.com				
KUZBARI Suzanne	Département de Génétique UFR de Génétique Moléculaire	suzanne.kuzbari@aphp.fr				
KYNAST Katharina	NCT Tissue Bank Pathologisches Institut Universität Heidelberg	katharina.kynast@med.uni-heidelberg.de			X	
LARGEAU Marine	REGP - Centre de ressources biologiques et tumorothèque	marine.largeau@aphp.fr			X	
LE MEUR Sébastien	CRB Santé Brest	sebastien.lemeur@chu-brest.fr			X	
LEROY Céline	INSERM CIC1433	c.eroy@chru-nancy.fr			X	
LESUEUR Fabienne	Inserm U900	fabienne.lesueur@curie.fr				
LOMAZZI Sandra	CRB LORRAIN - CHRU NANCY	s.lomazzi@chru-nancy.fr			X	
LORIMIER PHILIPPE	CENTRE DE RESSOURCES BIOLOGIQUES CHU	plorimier@chu-grenoble.fr				
MALLET David	DRCI CHU NICE	mallet.d@chu-nice.fr				

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
				Y	N	
MALSERVET Nicolas	BIOBANQUES	nicolas.malservet@inserm.fr				
Malzac Aurélie	Institut Paoli Calmettes	malzaca@pc.unicancer.fr			X	
Manivet Philippe	CRB-LRB	philippe.manivet@aphp.fr				
MARIANI Odette	INSTITUT CURIE	odette.mariani@curie.fr				
MAROT Gérard	IRELEC	irelec@irolec-alcen.com				
MEINUNG Bettina	Gorman Biobank Node (GBN)	meinung@apra.de			X	
MEKONG ADIOGO Elizabeth	BIOBANQUES	elizabeth.mekong-adiogo@inserm.fr				
MONTAGNE-STORA Samantha	INSTITUT JEROME LEJEUNE	celine.du.boispean@institutjeune.org				
MONTGERRAT Tora	FIMM	mtora@imim.es			X	
MUTTAQI Ubaida	BIOBANQUES	ubaida.muttaqi@inserm.fr				
LENATRE Fanny		fannylenatre@smcni.com			X	
FAVE Béatrice-Amandine	IRM Val de Saône	beatrice.fave@valdehone.com				
LORBUER Martina	Medical University Graz	martina.lorbuer@meduni-graz.at			X	

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Thursday May 19, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Attendees N ▶ Z

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
NASRI Saviz	CRB Tumorothèque CHU de Reims	snasri@chu-reims.fr		X		
NENUTIL Rudolf	Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute	nenuit@mou.cz				
ONOGORO OBRUCHE	UTM DREDGING LTD	attorneys@alexscottlawoffice.com				
ORTEGA-PAINO Eva	Lund University Dpt of Immunotechnology	eva.ortega-paino@immun.lth.se				
Ozkul Yusuf	Erciyes University	ozkans@erciyes.edu.tr				
Pace Nikolai	University of Malta	nikolai.p.pace@um.edu.mt				
PARDOUX Guillemette	BIOBANQUES	guillemette.pardoux@inserm.fr				

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
PASTERK Markus	BBMRI-ERIC	admin_dir@bbmri-eric.eu				
PERKMANN Thomas	Medizinische Universität Wien	thomas.perkmann@meduniwien.ac.at				
PERLAZA Blanca Liliana	Plate-forme iCARTE du Centre de Recherche Translationnel Investigation Clinique et	blanca-liliana.perlaza@pasteur.fr				
PIERRE-ARNAUD Faye	ICM-CRB	pierreaud.faye@gmail.com				
PIGEON Anna	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	anna.pigeon@live.fr				
PIROT Nelly	INSERM U1194	nelly.piro@inserm.fr				
Poirot-Mazères Isabelle	université Toulouse 1 capitoile	isabelle.poirot-mazeres@ut-capitoile.fr				
POLIZZI ANSELMO Annalisa	CRO Aviano NCI	a.polizzianselmo@libero.it		X		
POUHYET Claire	BIOBANQUES	claire.pouhyet@inserm.fr				
RAMON Olivier	Université de Nice Sophia Antipolis					
RENAUD Florence	CHRU Lille	florence.renaud@chru-lille.fr				
RIAL SEBBAG Emmanuelle	BIOBANQUES					

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
Ruckenbauer Christine	University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna	christine.ruckenbauer@vetmeduni.ac.at				
Rufenach Cornelia	Charité- German Biobank Node BBMRI.de	cornelia.rufenach@charite.de				
SCHMITT Sabrina	Tissue Bank of the NCT, Heidelberg University Hospital	Sabrina.schmitt@med.uni-heidelberg.de		X		
SERVAIS Marie-Dominique	Institut de Recherches Internationales SERVIER	marie-dominique.servais@servier.com		X		
SIVOUCFF Souhila	PremUp	sivoucsafa@gmail.com		X		
SOBRIER Marie-Laure	BIOBANQUES	marie-laure.sobrier@inserm.fr				
SONG Yutong	Shanghai Clinical Research Center	yulong.song@scrcnet.org				
SOUDJAY Djamilia	BIOBANQUES	djamilia.soudjay@inserm.fr				
TISSOT Lucie	CHRU BESANCON	lissot@chu-besancon.fr				
VASSEUR Stéphane	Myobank Institut de Myologie	s.vasseur@institut-myologie.org			X	
VIARD Patricia	CHU de Rennes	patricia.VIARD@chu-Rennes.fr				
VIVIEN Denis	CHU Caen	vivien@cyceron.fr				
Walter Ingrid	University of Veterinary Medicine	ingrid.walter@vetmeduni.ac.at		X		
Wieser Monika	University of Veterinary Medicine	monika.wieser@vetmeduni.ac.at		X		

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
Wutte Andrea	BBMRI-ERIC	andrea.wutte@bbmri-eric.eu				
YANNING Cai	Capital Medical University de Pékin					
YONGLI Guo	Capital Medical University de Pékin	guoyongli@bjuh.com.cn		X		

BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Thursday May 19, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Sponsor

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N	
DIDIERJEAN Olivier	AFFYMETRIX	Olivier_Didierjean@affymetrix.com				
KELLNREITER Niklas	AFFYMETRIX	Niklas_Kellnreiter@affymetrix.com				
TEYSSIER Franck	AFFYMETRIX	Franck_Teyssier@affymetrix.com			✓	
LEGUILLON Bernard	FROILABO	b.leguillon@froilabo.com				
REBMANN Julien	FROILABO	j.rebmann@froilabo.com			✓	
MAHJOUB Walid	FROILABO	w.mahjoub@froilabo.com			✓	
DOMENJOZ Cyril	GRIENER BIOONE	Cyril.Domenjoz@gbo.com				
DOWING Jason	Illumina	jdowning@illumina.com				

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance Y N	
VACHER Coralie	Illumina	cvacher@illumina.com			✓	
de MONTALIER Axel	MODUL BIO	a.demontalier@modulbio.com			✓	
Hugo BAYLE	MODUL BIO	h.bayle@modulbio.com				
JACOTOT Laurent	MODUL BIO	l.jacotot@modulbio.com			✓	
de JONG Mark	PROTEIGENE	mark.jong@fluidx.eu				
DUPONT Carole	PROTEIGENE	Carole.Dupont@brooks.com				
GEMONET Jonathan	PROTEIGENE	gemonet@proteigene.com				
OMASSON Alain	PROTEIGENE	omasson@proteigene.com				
KROME Jürgen	SYSMEX	Krome.Juergen@sysmex-europe.com				
BARTHELEMY-BLANC Rémi	TECHNIDATA	remi.barthelemy-blanc@technidata-web.com				
CHEYNET Stéphane	TECHNIDATA	stephane.cheynet@technidata-web.com				

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
VAUGHT Jim	ISBER	jvaught44@gmail.com				
WANG Peng		wangpeng@ccmu.edu.cn				
WATSON Peter	BC Cancer Agency, Vancouver Island Center	pwatson@bccancer.bc.ca				
WICHMANN Erich	Institute of Epidemiology at the Helmholtz Center Munich	wichmann@helmholtz-muenchen.de				
YUILLE Martin		martin.yuille@manchester.ac.uk				
ZAOMI Myriam	BIOBANQUES	myriam.zaomi@inserm.fr			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
ZATLOUKAL Kurt	BBMRI.at	kurt.zatoukal@medun-l-graz.at				

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BIOBANKING NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES MEETING
Thursday May 19, 2016
Hôtel St Paul - 29, bd Franck Pilatte - 06000 NICE

Attendance Sheet - Intervenants

NAME	INSTITUTION	email	Image right - Signature <i>In accordance with the law, by signing this form, I give permission to the Biobanques infrastructure and the University of Nice for photographs and film/video recordings of me to be captured during the aforementioned meeting. I understand that some of these images and recordings may be used by Biobanques and the University of Nice for communication purposes in the future.</i>	PRESENCE		
				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
BECKER Karl Friedrich	Universität München-Institut für pathologie	kf.becker@tum.de				
BJORKMANN Jens	TATAA Biocenter - Göteborg	Jens.bjorkman@tataa.com				
BONNET Jacques	Bordeaux University	botnet@imagene.eu				
CLEMENT Bruno	BIOBANQUES - INSERM-CRBs Foie Rennes	bruno.clement@inserm.fr				
DAGHER Georges	BIOBANQUES - INSERM	georges.dagher@inserm.fr				
DAIDONE Maria Grazia	Istituto Tumori, Milan, Italy	MariaGrazia.Daidone@istitutumori.mi.it				
DUYCKAERTS Charles	ICM	charles.duyckaerts@p.sl.sph.fr				

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This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

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				Signature	Certificate of attendance	
					Y	N
ERB Gilles	Roche diagnostics, France	gilles.erb@roche.com				
GERLIER Denis	CIRI Lyon	denis.gerlier@inserm.fr				
HASLACHER Helmut HASLACHER Helmut	Medizinische Universität Wien	helmuth.haslacher@meduniwien.ac.at		X		
HOFMAN Paul	CHU Nice	HOFMAN.P@chu-nice.fr				
HOLLMAN Suzanne	Université Potsdam	sholiman@uni-potsdam.de				
HUPPETZ Berthold	Medical University of Graz, Austria	biobank@medunigraz.at				
JUNOT Christophe	MetahubCEA, Paris	Christophe.JUNOT@cea.fr				
KREMER Andreas	itrm Solutions	andreas.kremer@itrm-solutions.com				
LAVITRANO Marie-Luisa	BBMRI.it	marialuisa.lavitrano@unimib.it				
LAWLOR Rila T.	ARC - University of Verona-Italy	rla.lawlor@arc-net.it				
LITTON Jan Eric	BBMRI	secretary@bbmri-eric.eu				

Appendix III - Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians

Agenda

International Agency for Research on Cancer

World Health
 Organization

IARC-BCNet – BBMRI-ERIC

**Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians
 (22 – 23 May 2017)**

**and Open Forum
 (24 May 2017)**

Children’s Cancer Hospital, Egypt – CCHE 57357

TRAINING AGENDA (22 - 23 May 2017)

Day 1 Monday 22 May 2017

08:00-08:30 Registration

Introduction (Chair: Dr Maimuna Mendy)

08:30-08:45 Welcome to CCHE Dr Sherif Abou ElNaga, CEO
 Dr Rania Labib (15’)

08:45-09:00 Introduction of Participants All

09:00-09:15 Overview of the training¹ Dr Marianne Henderson
 Ms Anouk Berger (15’)

09:15-10:00 Introduction to Biobanking Dr Maimuna Mendy (20’)
 Dr Marianne Henderson (25’)
 recorded

10:00-10:30 Coffee

¹ Technicians will complete basic CTRNet biobank training prior to the training workshop
 This course and open forum is co-funded by the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project grant nr 676550 H2020

Session 1: Importance of Pathology in Biobanking (Chair: Dr Hala Taha)

10:30-11:10	The Role of the Pathologist	
	1. Pre-analytical Steps in Sample Handling: General overview, including warm/cold ischemia, transportation, documentation	Dr Maher Sughayer (20")
	2. Molecular pathology: Quality Practices and their effect on downstream analysis; DNA, RNA extractions, documentation	Dr Rita Lawlor Dr Maher Sughayer (20")

Session 2: Quality Management of Tissue Samples for Biobanking (Chair: Dr Rania Labib)

11:10-11:25	What you need to know when developing SOPs	Dr Elodie Caboux (15")
11:25-11:40	Introduction to Quality Management in biobanking (QA and QC)	Dr Maimuna Mendy (15")
11:40-12:00	The principles of ICDO coding, Cancer Registry and Linking to biobanks	Dr Sameera Ezzat (20")
12:00-13:00	Break out session I (Discussion topics)	Ms Anouk Berger
	1. How do the topics relate to your institution?	Dr Maher Sughayer
	2. What challenges do you face at your institution in ensuring that SOPs in relation to tissue handling are developed and adhered to for increased tissue quality?	Dr Sameera Ezzat Dr Rania Labib
	3. As pathologists and path/histo technicians, could you share examples with the group of how you have (or can) influenced procedures upstream of biobanking? i.e from surgery to the transportation of samples to the pathology lab.	Dr Maimuna Mendy
	4. In your setting, how do you think pathologists can contribute to research? What are some of the expected benefits in participating in research? If you have participated in research, have these benefits been realized?	
13:00-14:00	Lunch – Cafeteria	

This course and open forum is co-funded by the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project grant nr 676550 H2020

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

14:00-15:00	<p>Break out session II</p> <p>(Discussion topics)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the main diseases and types of tissue samples you collect? What types of quality issues must be addressed when processing these tissues 2. How does quality of tissues affect the different diagnostics procedures carried out in your pathology lab? 3. What are the ethics challenges you encounter when working with/donating samples to biobanks? 4. Do you participate in research, if so, what type? 	<p>Ms Anouk Berger</p> <p>Dr Maher Sughayer Dr Sameera Ezzat Dr Rania Labib Dr Elodie Caboux</p>
15:00-16:00	<p>Tea</p>	
16:00-17:00	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction of CEN norms / ISO TC 276 2. Minimum data / what is the proper way to record this data? 3. CAP Accreditation 	<p>Dr Elodie Caboux (20")</p> <p>Dr Rania Labib (20")</p> <p>Dr Maher Sughayer (20")</p>
17:00-18:00	<p>Report Back from Break Out Session I</p>	<p>Ms Anouk Berger</p>

This course and open forum is co-funded by the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project grant nr 676550 H2020

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Day 2 Tuesday 23 May, 2017

**Session 3: Ensuring quality in the biobank: The connection to the Pathology Suite
 (Chair: Dr Maher Sughayer)**

08:00-09:00	Tour of the hospital	
09:00-11:00	Theoretical session and discussions 1. Review of available ancillary diagnostic methods (presentation) 2. Examples of managing the inclusion of pathology samples in research projects 3. Report back from Break Out Session II	Dr Hala Taha (30') Dr Asmaa Salama (15') ALL (60")
11:00-11:30	Coffee	
11:30-13:00	Practical Session I Pathology Lab Orientation 1. Hands on: tissue receiving, types of tissues received 2. Grossing e.g kidney grossing and sample banking 3. Tissue processing and embedding, and slides 4. Ancillary Techniques <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immunohistochemistry • FISH technique • Molecular techniques • 	Dr Hala Taha (10") Dr Mohamed Hussein (30") Dr Hala Taha (10") Dr Asmaa Salama (15") Dr Naglaa El-Kinaii (15") Dr Maha Yehia (15")
13:00-14:00	Lunch	
14:00-15:30	Practical Session II Biobank Orientation 1. Tour of the biobank 2. Getting surgery list and sending request forms to pathology 3. Overview of data associated with samples	Dr Rania Labib and team (15") Dr Rania Labib (15") Dr Maram Alaa (60")
15:30-16:00	Coffee	
16:00-18:00	Practical Session III Clinical Research and biobanks 1. Standardizing the data collection for clinical research 2. Supporting the IT infrastructure for the biobank 3. Integrating the clinical data and cancer registry with the biobank 4. The Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics 5. Participants present their posters ²	Dr Mohammed Kamal (15") Eng Hassan Elwy (15") Dr Omneya Hassanian (15") Dr Kyriacos Kyriacou (10") ALL (65")
18:00-18:30	Feedback and Evaluation	Ms Anouk Berger

² Participants will be provided with powerpoint templates to complete before the training.
 This course and open forum is co-funded by the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project grant nr 676550 H2020

Open Forum 24 May 2017

session is open to BCNet training participants and the general public

Chair: Markus Pasterk/Maimuna Mendy

08:30-09:00	Registration	
09:00-09:15	Welcome and Presentation of CCHE 57357	Dr Rania Labib (15")
09:15-19:30	IARC-BCNet	Dr Elodie Caboux (15")
09:30-09:45	BBMRI-ERIC – introduction and how we work	Dr Markus Pasterk (15")
09:45-10:15	Ethics in Biobanking 1. The ethics considerations in sample and data sharing-international guidelines and regulations 2. The Legal Ethics and Governance Framework for Best Practice in Genomic Research and Biobanking in Africa	Dr Jessica Wright /Dr Maimuna Mendy (30")
10:15-10:45	An example of how Ethics committees in Africa are addressing Biobanking: 1. The Nigerian Experience 2. The Ugandan Experience	Dr Ilyasu Zubairu (15") Dr Erisa Mwaka (15")
10:45-11:00	Biobanking in Egypt/Egypt Biobank Task Force	Dr Wagida Anwar (15")
11:00-11:30	Coffee	
11:30-13:00	Break-out/discussion groups Questions for the groups 1. The pros and cons of broad consent in the Egyptian setting 2. The role of Ethics Committees and the review process for biobanking projects 3. Improving Egypt's participation in international research. 4. Highlight success stories of international efforts.	Mr Markus Pasterk/ Dr Wagida Anwar
13:00-14:00	Lunch	
14:00-14:15	The need for Sustainability of Biobanking resources	Dr Marianne Henderson (15")- recorded
14:15-14:30	Legal Aspects of Biobanking in Egypt	Dr Azza Saleh (15")
14:30-15:30	Discussion and Feedback	Dr Maimuna Mendy
15:30-16:00	Coffee	
16:00-17:30	Questions and Answers, Reporting, Summary, Close of Meeting	Dr Maimuna Mendy

This course and open forum is co-funded by the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project grant nr 676550 H2020

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Attendance list

Number	Country	Institution	Pathologists	Technicians	BCNet	Emails
1	Egypt	Kasr Al Ainy Hospital Faculty of Medicine	Dalia Omran Professor		Yes	daliaomran@kasralainy.edu.eg
2	Egypt	Medical Research Institute - Alexandria University	Mohamed Ata; assistant lecturer	Aysha Esam, assistant lecturer	Yes	ata14786@yahoo.com aysha85@outlook.com
3	Egypt	National Cancer Institute Biobank - Cairo University	Omar Dahrog, Technologist	Iman Taha Technologist	Yes	omardhrog0123@gmail.com imanisma3iltaha@hotmail.com
4	Egypt	national liver institute	Asmaa mosbeh, assistant researcher	Dina mostafa Sweed assistant lecturer	Yes	asmaamosbeh@hotmail.com dr.dinasweed@yahoo.com
5	Egypt	Theodor Bilharz Research Institute	Sarah Hassan Tawfik Associate Researcher		Yes	sarah_tbri@yahoo.com
6	Ethiopia	Jigjiga University	Dr Abdulaziz Ibrahim Head of Referral Hospital	Mr Adugna Negussie Medical College, Senior	No	gemacid@gmail.com adugalab@gmail.com
7	Gambia, The	Edward Francis Small Teaching Hospital	Ousman Leigh	Modou Salieu Jallow Medical laboratory	No	leighousman80@gmail.com momodousalieujallow85@yahoo
8	Ghana	Breast Care International International		BISMARCK MENSAH Laboratory Technologist	Yes	fifi_bisey@yahoo.com
9	Ghana	University of Ghana	Dr Afua Abrahams Consultant	Cecilia Botwe	NO	aodabrahams@ug.edu.gh cella20h@yahoo.com
10	Indonesia	Department of Pathological Anatomy	Ery Kus Dwianingsih	Hanggoro Tri Rinonce	Yes	ery_malueka@ugm.ac.id hanggoro_rinonce@ugm.ac.id
11	Jordan	King Hussein Cancer Center	Maxim Research pathologist		YES	mashhab@khcc.jo
12	Kenya	Aga Khan University Hospital, Nairobi	Shahin Sayed Pathologist	Susan Ngugi Section Head Histology	NO	shaheen.sayed@aku.edu susan.ngugi@aku.edu
13	Mexico	Instituto Nacional de Cancerologia	Dr Luz Ruiz Godoy	Dr. Lourdes Suarez Affiliated pathologist	YES	lrmrgodoyr@gmail.com lusuroa@gmail.com
14	Nigeria	College of Medicine, University of Ibadan	Ayodeji Salami Pathologist	Bobola Farinloye, Lab Scientist	YES	ayodejisalami@gmail.com
15	Nigeria	Obafemi Awolowo University, ILE-IFE, OSUN STATE	Akinwumi Komolafe Consultant Pathologist	Adegoke Aremu Histoscientist	NO	akinkomo1@yahoo.com adegokearemu34@yahoo.com
16	Nigeria	University of Abuja	Dr. Olabode Peter Oluwole	Dr. Bawa Abimiku Senior Lecturer	NO	olabode166@gmail.com abimikub@yahoo.com
17	Senegal	Hopital Général de Grand Yoff	Aissatou Ndiaye Major technician		NO	aissytu@yahoo.fr
18	Sudan	Alzaiem Alazhari University	Ihsan Abdelhalim pathologist		YES	ihsanosman@hotmail.com
19	Tanzania	KCRI/KCMC	Alex Mremi Head of Dept/Pathologist, Mmed Path	Daniel Mbwambo Histotechnologist, BSc	Yes	alexmremi@gmail.com mbwambodannie@gmail.com
20	Uganda	St. Mary's Hospital Lacor (Gulu)	Caroline Achola	Michael Odong Laboratory technologist	NO	michaeldng2@gmail.com carolachola@yahoo.com
21	Zambia	University Teaching Hospital University of Zambia	Peter Davies Julius Pathologist	Anglin Hamasuku Biomedical Scientist	NO	pmatashij@gmail.com ahamasuku@yahoo.com

Presentations

IARC-BCNet
**Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and
Pathology / Histology Technicians**
Children's Cancer Hospital, Egypt – CCEH 57357

Marianne K. Henderson, Co-Chair, Education and Training, BCNet
Anouk Berger, Co-Chair, Education and Training, BCNet

NATIONAL CANCER INSTITUTE May 22-24, 2017

Practical Training & Discussions
22 - 23 May 2017

*Thank you for taking the online training provided through the ISBER Portal

NATIONAL CANCER INSTITUTE

Open Forum:
Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues In Biobanking
24 May 2017

*session is open to BCNet training participants and the general public

NATIONAL CANCER INSTITUTE

www.cancer.gov www.cancer.gov/espanol

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

BCNet and BBMRI-ERIC Training in Biobanking
 for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology
 Technicians

22-24 May 2017
 CCHE-57357, Cairo, Egypt

Presenting yourself on the learning space
 N= 21 participants & faculty members

Tell us about your priorities
 Survey Results
 N= 22 respondents/ 31 training participants

Top 10 priorities - Pathology Technicians

Introduction to Biobanking – Part II:
 The continuum from the patient
 to the biobank to research and back

Marianne K Henderson, M.S.
 Senior Advisor on Biobanking, Center for Global Health,
 Senior Advisor for Division Resources, Division of Cancer Epidemiology and Genetics

22 May 2017

Marianne K. Henderson, MS

Trained in the Laboratory of Genetics at NCI, molecular genetics studies in mice
 Operations Chief for the Division of Cancer Epidemiology and Genetics, NCI (17 years) – large
 biorepository operation (12+ M specimens from epidemiology studies across the world), current
 Senior Advisor for Division Resources
 Senior Advisor on Biobanking, Center for Global Health, NCI
 Active in the International Society for Biological and Environmental Repositories (ISBER) since
 1999
 ISBER President 2011-12 (3-year term includes Pres-Elect and Past Pres years)
 Chair, ISBER Organizing Advisory Committee (2013-19)
 Co-Chair, Global Biobank Week Sept 2017
 US Interagency Committee on Scientific Collections
 Advisory Boards – BBMRI se, BBMRI-LPC

Outline

1. Human health and the key role of biobanking – globally, regionally and locally.
2. What is biobanking and its continuum
3. Biobanking must be harmonized
4. Tools to support our biobank community

Imagine:

Through your clinical services and laboratory research, you can better understand diseases that impact the health of your community and potential preventions, early detection, treatments, and cures...

Quality local biobanking is one of the keys to that understanding...

But what does that really mean?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 676550.

Introduction to Biobanking I: the key components including Ethics Legal and Social Issues in Biobanking

Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians CCHE 57357, Cairo-22 – 23 May 2017

International Agency for Research on Cancer
Lyon, France

Dr Maimuna Mendy, Head LSB Group
mendym@iarc.fr; ibb.iarc.fr; bcnet.iarc.fr

International Agency for Research on Cancer
World Health Organization

- **Group Head of IARC Laboratory Services and Biobank**
- Molecular Virologist, Over 30 years experience in hepatitis and HCC research
- Founder and co-ordinator of BCNet Member of BBMRI-ERIC (MC and AOM)
- Advisory Committee Member and IEC (GET; WAHO Regional Biobank, Polish National Biobank, H3Africa)
- Member of several biobank organisation and societies; ISBER, ESSBB,
- PI/WP leader for several EU H2020 funded project (B3Africa, Prolifica)

International Agency for Research on Cancer
World Health Organization

The purpose of the Biobank training for Pathologists and technicians?

- Pathologists provide diagnostic services primarily for patient care but also important for the accurate validation of biobank tissues included in research
- The adoption of biobanking principles in pathology will accelerate the use of evidence based best practise, guidelines and SOPs for pre-analytical processing to obtain quality samples and data.
- Thus the objective of the training is to empower participants to improve your procedures and to recognise the important role you play in cancer research

International Agency for Research on Cancer
World Health Organization

Overview

1. Introduction
2. Biobank definitions, infrastructure and component
3. Ethics, Legal and Social Issues

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World Health Organization

The Role of the Pathologist in Biobanking

Maher A. Sughayer M.D; FCAP
Chair, Dept. of Pathology
Director of Biobank, King Hussein Cancer Center,
Amman, Jordan

Key Role

- Pathologists are the custodians of tissues removed at surgery.
- They are legally responsible for any tissues removed from human beings for the purposes of diagnosis or treatment.
- Patient's welfare and interest comes first.

Standard Operation Procedures

- The collection, processing, storage and transportation of samples are simply procedures
- And before carrying out any procedure we need a written set of instructions: so that the procedure is done in a standardized consistent fashion every time and by every body to produce a Quality product: we need SOP's.

- So SOP's are a must for an intra institutional standardization, but a country-wide, network-wide or worldwide (universal) unified SOP's are the ideal situations for quality specimens leading to quality research thus unifying the preanalytical variables and eliminating bias.
- Nevertheless; always implement the SOP! In a precise way

The Role of the Pathologist

Molecular pathology: Quality Practices and their effect on downstream analysis; DNA, RNA extractions

Rita T. Lawlor

Department of Diagnostics and Public Health – University of Verona
ARC-NET – Applied Research on Cancer Centre

THE PATHOLOGIST IN THE MIX

- Specimen Procurement
- Diagnostic decision and annotations
- Sample Revision

THE PATHOLOGIST IN THE MIX

Recommendations

R7: No tissue banking for research should take place without proper pathology documentation. All specimens used within research programs must have been reviewed and assessed by a pathologist.

R8: The standard for tissue banking is a tissue sample and not derived products or isolated molecules.

R9: The pathologist should have an active participation in decisions of access to banked specimens.

R10: Efforts should be made to better communicate the role of pathology in tissue banking.

DNA EXTRACTION PROCESS

The pre-analytical steps that need standardization and quality control in order to obtain consistent results from DNA/RNA analysis are **three**:

- preparation and storage conditions of tissue/biological materials;
- DNA/RNA extraction methods;
- DNA/RNA qualification.

What do you need to know when developing SOPs?

International Agency for Research on Cancer
Lyon, France

Dr Elodie CABOUX
IARC-BCNet – BBMRI-ERIC Pathology Training
22 – 23 May 2017

What is a SOP?

ISBER definition: "accurate descriptions of tasks performed and verification of activities by more than one repository technician or by a supervisor"

IARC definition: "A set of detailed written instructions to achieve uniformity of the performance of a specific function"

A **written** procedure of **step-by-step** instructions compiled to help workers to carry out routine operations. SOPs aim to achieve **efficiency**, **quality** output and **uniformity** of performance, while reducing miscommunication, non-conformities and failure.

SOPs are issued to specifically instruct staff in areas of responsibility, work instructions, appropriate specifications and required records.

Why a SOP is needed?

- ✓ To ensure compliance standards are met
- ✓ To ensure the procedure has no adverse impact
- ✓ To ensure safety
- ✓ To ensure everything goes according to schedule
- ✓ To prevent failures in processing
- ✓ To ensure that each task in a process is performed the same way every time
- ✓ To be used as training document

Types of SOP

- ✓ **Administrative or functional procedure**
 - Reviewing documentation such as contracts, QM plans
 - Determining organizational training needs
- ✓ **Technical activity:**
 - how to perform a specific analytical method to be followed in the laboratory?
 - how to collect and process a sample?
 - how to collect and process data?

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Introduction to Quality in Biobanking

Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology /
Histology Technicians (22 – 24 May 2017)

International Agency for Research on Cancer
Lyon, France

Dr Maimuna Mendy, Head LSB Group
mendym@iarc.fr; ibb.iarc.fr; bcnet.iarc.fr

Overview

Introducing the following terminologies:

1. Interoperability
2. Quality Management Systems
3. Quality Assurance
4. Quality Control
5. Standardisation
6. Certification
7. Accreditation

Why conduct cancer research?

The purpose of conducting cancer research is that:

- ✓ All cancer could be prevented, that if cancer occurred, it could be diagnosed quickly, easily and accurately.
- ✓ Once diagnosed, that all cancer could be cured quickly, easily and effectively and treatment is specific and not toxic to the patient.

What is the problem?

- ✓ There are not enough quality tissue and human biosamples and information on:
 - The quality of the sample and the way it has been collected, processed, stored and transported
 - The person who donated the sample, their disease, treatment and outcome is also not always available
- ✓ Samples and data may not be interoperable between biobanks
 - Single institutions cannot provide end-to-end comprehensive service
 - Different sample and data collection protocol
 - Different ethics and regulatory framework

The principles of ICDO coding, Cancer Registry and Linking to biobanks

Sameera Ezzat, MD, PhD
 Professor and Chair of Epidemiology and Preventive Medicine Department
 Director of NLISSI CRC
 National Liver Institute,
 Menoufia university
 Egypt

Outline

- **Cancer registry:**
Definition, history, types and importance
- **ICD-O3 coding**
- **Linking registry to biobanks**

Outline

- **Cancer registry:**
Definition, history, types and importance
- ICD-O3 coding
- Linking registry to biobanks

Definition

- **The cancer registry** is a
- systematic collection,
- storage,
- analysis,
- interpretation and
- reporting of data on subjects with cancer.

Introduction to CEN norms / ISO / TC 276

International Agency for Research on Cancer
Lyon, France

Dr Elodie CABOUX
IARC-BCNet – BBMRI-ERIC Pathology Training
22 – 23 May 2017

International Agency for Research on Cancer
World Health Organization

Why quality is needed?

"Preanalytical errors still account for nearly 60%-70% of all problems occurring in laboratory diagnostics, most of them attributable to mishandling procedures during collection, handling, preparing or storing the specimens."

Lippi G. et al. Preanalytical quality improvement: from dream to reality. Clin Chem Lab Med. 2011;49(7):1123-26

The challenge for a biobank...

Sample valuable for any future purpose:

- To foresee the future
- To be able to provide a complete documentation of the entire process chain from "donor to storage" based on validated methods and standardised protocols.

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Quality for a biobank...

SOPs + CEN/ISO

**STANDARDIZATION
HARMONIZATION**

International Agency for Research on Cancer
World Health Organization

Human Biobanks Data Standards

Rania Mohamed Labib, PhD, MSc
 Head of Biorepository and Biospecimen Research
 CAP Certified Biorepository Inspector,
 ISBER Certified Biobank Professional,
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CCHE Vision

To be the unique worldwide icon of change towards a cancer-free childhood

CCHE BIOREPOSITORY

Vision
Foster Research ...Promote Cure

Centralized Biorepository and Biospecimen Research Unit **linked with clinical data** to be one of CCHE- **core facilities** that enable integrating research into services

BIOBANK CHEAT SHEET WHAT IS A BIOBANK ?

- Organized collection of logical samples
- Stored long-term
- Searchable, data rich
- Used for research
- Regulated by ethics and law

Value is both in the nitrogen tanks and the database...

Take as much care of your data as you do of your biological specimens.

Accreditation for Biorepositories

“College of American Pathologists (CAP) as an example”

Maher A. Sughayer M.D; FCAP
 Chair, Dept. of Pathology
 Director of Biobank, King Hussein Cancer Center,
 Amman, Jordan

Why accreditation ??

2

Why Accreditation??

- To assure patient's safety through quality
- To assure quality/Excellence in laboratory determinations
- Competency to perform specific testing procedures
- There is a documented quality system, that is fully operational, and addresses and conforms to all elements of ISO 15189 or CAP
- The lab is operating in accordance with the required quality system
- Adherence to regulatory requirements

Why Accreditation/QMP?

- Reduce or eliminate medical errors.
- Meet customer requirements.
- Meet governmental/accreditation requirements.
- Sustaining quality objectives.
- **Patients safety.**

BCNet and BBMRI-ERIC Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians

Discussions

22-24 May 2017

CCHE-57357, Cairo, Egypt

- 1- How do the topics presented so far relate to your institution?
- 2- What challenges do you face at your institution in ensuring that SOPs in relation to tissue handling are developed and adhered to for increased tissue quality?
- 3- What are the ethics challenges you encounter when working with/donating samples to biobanks?
- 4- As pathologists and path/histo technicians, could you share examples with the group of how you have influenced (or could influence) procedures upstream of biobanking? i.e from surgery to the transportation of samples to the pathology lab.
- 5- In your setting, how do you think pathologists can contribute to research? What are some of the expected benefits in participating in research? If you have participated in research (what type?), have these benefits been realized?
- 6- What are the main diseases and types of tissue samples you collect? What types of quality issues must be addressed when processing these tissues?
- 7- How does quality of tissues affect the different diagnostics procedures carried out in your pathology lab?

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Review of Available Diagnostic Ancillary Methods

HALA TAHA SALEM
 Prof. Pathology, NCI, Cairo university
 Chief of pathology Dept. CCH-E

Overview

ANCILLARY part 1

- Routine Hx & E Slides
- Frozen Sections & Smears
- Immunohistochemical stains
- Special Stains

ANCILLARY part 2

- FCM
- Cyto genetics
- Molecular/ Cytogenetic testing
- PCR

PREANALYTICAL WORK UP

ACCESSION

- Bar Coded
- Request form
- Rejection policy
- Cassette printer

PREANALYTICAL WORK UP

Grossing

- CAP protocol.
- Digital Library.
- Tissue Banking.

Managing the inclusion of pathology samples in research projects

Dr. Asmaa Ibrahim Salama
 Consultant of Pathology
 CCHE 57357

PURPOSE

- To outline the procedures to be followed when a request has been made to use anatomical pathology specimens for research activities.
- To ensure that CCHE Anatomical Pathology Lab (AP lab) complies with all legislative and accreditation requirements, to assist in advancing knowledge through research.

POLICY

- CCHE AP Lab has a commitment to promote an environment that values research under strict guidelines and policies that control the best use as well as retention of Anatomical Pathology specimens.

- It also has to ensure:
 - 1- minimization of duplication among different researches.
 - 2- transparent and accountable research processes.

Ancillary techniques in Histopathology Part II

Dr Naglaa Elkinaai
 Assistant Professor of pathology , NCI, Cairo university
 Pathology Consultant at CCH-E

Flowcytometry

- ▶ Laser based technology used to measure the cellular physical / chemical properties while passing in single file in the apparatus.
- ▶ Allows For Detection Of **Surface Markers** Of Cells
- ▶ Allows For Detection Of **DNA Content**
- ▶ Allows for Detection of **cell cycle phases**

The Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics. The Cyprus School of Molecular Medicine

K. Kyriacou, PhD, FRMS
 Professor and Dean
 Head Dept. of EM/Molecular Pathology
 Bcnet : workshop May 2017

Name of the Biobank: The Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics

The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics

Established in 1990 as a bi-communal, non-profit Medical and Research Institution

- **Vision:** Function as a National and Regional centre of Excellence in the areas of Neurology, genetics, and Biomedical Sciences
- **Mission:** Provide high level Clinical and Laboratory services, develop advanced research programs and provide post-graduate education in the areas of Neurology, Genetics and other Sciences.

27 years later CING represents one of the most advanced organizations in Neurology and Biomedicine in the region. It manages more than 10,000 patients, offers 75,000 specialized tests and executes more than 40 research programs annually. CING receives 2 million euros in research funds every year.

A SCHOOL OF THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE OF NEUROLOGY & GENETICS

CYPRUS SCHOOL of molecular medicine

A SCHOOL OF THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE OF NEUROLOGY & GENETICS

CYPRUS SCHOOL of molecular medicine

CING – Clinics and Departments

- **Clinical Sciences Sector**
 - Neurology Clinics A-E
 - Clinical Genetics Clinic
- **Biomedical Sciences Sector**
 - Biochemical Genetics Dept.
 - Cardiovascular Genetics Dept. & Laboratory of Forensic Genetics
 - Cytogenetics & Genomics Dept.
 - Electron Microscopy & Molecular Pathology Dept
 - Molecular Genetics, Function & Therapy Dept.
 - Molecular Genetics Thalassaemia Dept.
 - Molecular Virology Dept.
 - Neurogenetics Dept.

A SCHOOL OF THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE OF NEUROLOGY & GENETICS

CYPRUS SCHOOL of molecular medicine

Thalassemia

- Genetic disease that is inherited as autosomal recessive and is caused by mutations in haemoglobin genes.
- Common in Cyprus: 1/6 Cypriots are carriers
- National prevention program in place for more than 30 years.
 - Detects carriers before marriage.
 - Genetic screening and prenatal diagnosis of all couples who are both carriers at the Institute.

A SCHOOL OF THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE OF NEUROLOGY & GENETICS

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BCNet and BBMRI-ERIC Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians

Discussion questions
22-24 May 2017
CCHE-57357, Cairo, Egypt

How do the topics presented so far relate to your institution?

Already a Biobank, but challenges regarding quality and link with cancer registry

How to exploit archived FFPE tissues for research? In general can be kept for 10 years or longer.

Cancer registry in the hospital, but how do we establish a biobank?

Important of setting up a system to get informed consent upfront in order not to have to re-contact participants after 10 years

Trying to establish both a cancer registry and a biobank

Improvement of SOPs and related pre-analytical steps

Issue with consenting patients for use of samples for research

Issues of coordination with the institution and government support

How to select a place to store our sample? Look for the closest good quality settings

What challenges do you face at your institution in ensuring that SOPs in relation to tissue handling are developed and adhered to for increased tissue quality?

No SOPs

- Even if SOPs are written, the issue is for staff to use them, especially senior ones
- Poor quality of specimens from OR (e.g. crushed tissues)
- No collaboration, not enough trust between stakeholders
- Lack on management training for physicians/researchers
- No investment from governments or institution to build biobanks
- Loosing leadership on the storage of own specimens

Coordination meetings

- Importance of initial training and continuing education at all levels
- Collaborations (i.e. requests to share sample) may help develop own storage capacity
- Key not to give everything away. No depletion of samples
- Basic infrastructure + QMS are sufficient to start sharing material. Technical support is available.
- Help biobank funding by including in grant for research projects

As pathologists and path/histo technicians, could you share examples with the group of how you have influenced (or could influence) procedures upstream of biobanking? i.e. from surgery to the transportation of samples to the pathology lab.

Communication for improved coordination (e.g. tell us in advance)

Narrow the divide between surgery and pathology (need regular meetings)

Provide support (e.g. feel free to call us)

Involved in initial training / continuing education of key stakeholders

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Biobank Network for Low and Middle Income Countries (BCNet)
 International Agency for Research on Cancer
 Lyon, France

Dr Elodie CABOUX
 IARC-BCNet – BBMRI-ERIC Pathology Training
 22 – 23 May 2017

International Agency for Research on Cancer
 World Health Organization

IARC biobank samples

International Agency for Research on Cancer
 World Health Organization

BCNet- Background

- Global cancer incidence rates projected to increase by 60% to 21 million by 2030 (<http://globocan.iarc.fr/>).
- About half of all cancer deaths expected in LMICs, and most of these in African countries.
- Under representation of quality biological resources for scientific research in LMIC.

International Agency for Research on Cancer
 World Health Organization

Biobanks as important infrastructure for research

- Investments in research infrastructure in high income countries (HIC) have greatly increased to support research, scientific advancement and innovation.
- Investments in infrastructure to provide high quality samples and data have so far not been replicated in LMICs.
- IARC decided to form a **LMIC biobank cohort building network (BCNet)** in its effort to address this shortfall (2013).
- BCNet aim is to promote and support biobanking activities and research infrastructure in LMICs.

International Agency for Research on Cancer
 World Health Organization

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

BBMRI-ERIC
 Biobanking and
 BioMolecular resources
 Research Infrastructure

BBMRI-ERIC – Introduction, services and more
 Prof. Markus Pasterk

Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology/Histology Technicians and Open Forum
 Children's Cancer Hospital, Egypt – CHE 57357, 22-24 May 2017

www.bbMRI-eric.eu

What is BBMRI-ERIC?

- BBMRI-ERIC is Europe's Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure.
- It was setup in 2013 to
 - facilitate access to samples and data;
 - harmonise procedures and implement common standards;
 - **build up capacities.**

This training course is supported by the H2020 ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project, grant nr. 676550

BBMRI-ERIC Mission

BBMRI-ERIC will **increase efficacy** and **excellence** of European bio-medical research:

- by **facilitating access** to quality-defined human health/disease-relevant biological resources including associated data in an efficient and ethically and legally compliant manner,
- by reducing the fragmentation of the bio-medical research landscape through **harmonization of procedures, implementation of common standards** and fostering high-level collaboration,
- by **capacity building** in countries with less developed biobanking communities thereby contributing to Europe's cohesion policy and strengthening the ERA.

BBMRI-ERIC Membership

Members of BBMRI-ERIC

Austria
 Belgium
 Czech Republic
 Estonia
 Finland
 France
 Germany
 Greece
 Italy
 Latvia
 Malta
 The Netherlands
 Norway
 Poland
 Sweden
 United Kingdom

Observers of BBMRI-ERIC

Switzerland
 Turkey
 IARC

Ethical considerations in sample and data sharing – international guidelines and regulations

Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians (22 – 24 May 2017)

International Agency for Research on Cancer
 Lyon, France

Maimuna Mendy, Head IARC Biobank: mendym@iarc.fr
 Jessica Wright, University of Sheffield

Contents

- Biobank definition and types
- Ethics in Biobanking and international guidelines
- Data and sample sharing
- Summary

Biobank Definition

Biobank is a collection of biological materials and the associated data, stored in an organized system, for a population or a large subset of a population for research (OECD)

Biobank collections also includes non-human organisms, such as plants, animals, fungi, and bacteria

Biobank types

Disease-based biobanks- hospital embedded

- Collection of samples and clinical data from disease patients
- To support diagnosis and ongoing care

Population-based biobanks - to support population cohorts

- Collection of samples and data
- Target group mostly without disease

Follow-up for disease occurrence

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Ethical issues in Biobanking The Nigerian Experience

Prof. Zubairu Iliyasu
 Chair, NHREC, Nigeria

Outline

- Background
 - definitions, storage and utility
- Biobanks in Nigeria
- Ethical issues in biobanking
 - informed consent
 - sample and data sharing
 - ownership of samples
 - return of results
 - Governance framework
- Nigeria' experience
- Conclusions

Definitions

- A **biobank** is a repository that stores biological samples from human or non-human sources derived from research, medical or veterinary practice
- All biological materials stored for more than 2 months after analysis in the context of routine medical practice are considered to be "banked" samples except organs stored for transplantation.

Storage and utility

- Banked samples may be stored indefinitely or for a specified period of time and typically contain identifying information or can be traced back to their origin
- Biobanks provide researchers with access to samples and a minimal set of relevant data about the source of the materials in the biobank

Biobanking The Ugandan experience

Dr. Mwaka Erisa, PhD
 College of Health Sciences,
 Makerere, Uganda

Children's Cancer Hospital, Cairo Egypt
 24th May 2017

Introduction

- Uganda has only one officially approved biobank
- *Integrated Biorepository of H3Africa Uganda (IBRH3AU) at MakCHS.*
- Approval by REC and UNCST
- Projected total storage capacity: 400,000
- Currently 120,000 stored samples in local archive
- Shipped over 600,000 samples over last few years
- Many repositories

IBRH₃AU Governance structure

Figure 1: The governance structure of the IBRH₃AU

Bioinformatics Centre

- Uganda Medical Informatics Centre
- Uganda Virus Research Institute.
- Aims to build and operate a high-throughput medical bioinformatics data centre in sub-Saharan Africa.
- build local capacity in bioinformatics and enable local scientists to share data medical
- Record storage for at least 5 years

Sustaining Biobanks: Insights from Infrastructure Planning across the World

Marianne K. Henderson, M.S.
*Senior Advisor for Division Resources, OD
 Division of Cancer Epidemiology and Genetics,
 Senior Advisor for Biobanking,
 Center for Global Health*

24 May 2017

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Biobanking Drivers

- Increasing Emphasis on Personalized Medicine and Companion Diagnostics
 Biomarker research can support targeted medicine in the future
- Continued Growth in Translational Medicine and Epidemiology
 Biospecimens enable research and clinical trials on large representative population samples in order to find causal relationships with disease.
- Response to Global Health/Global Diseases
 Response to epidemics, chronic disease and globalized disease management.
- Demand for Advanced Sample Management Services
 Basic sample storage solutions are no longer adequate to meet the stringent market and regulatory demands for research and drug discovery trials.

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Biobanks around the world come in many different "types"

A Biobank's purpose contributes to its...

- ❖ Focus and goals
- ❖ Donor population (collection type)
- ❖ Intended use and/or fit for purpose
- ❖ Utilization rates or temporal profile

But one overall condition that most biobanks have in common is...

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Sustainability Global Discussions / Local Worries (US Data, n=426)

Category	Percentage
major	40%
moderate	31%
minor	20%
not at all	9%

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Legal Framework of Clinical Research Oversight in Egypt

Prof. Azza Saleh

Open Forum 24 May 2017
 Children's Cancer Hospital, Egypt – CCHH 57357

The 1st

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Appendix IV Bridging biobanks in MENA countries to promote research and Healthcare and Workshop on Biobanking for Rare Diseases

Agenda and Flyers

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON BIOBANKING FOR RARE DISEASES
May 2nd 2018

08:00 - 09:00	Registration
09:00 - 09:15	Welcome and Introduction (Mehmet Öztürk)
09:15 - 09:30	Goals of the Workshop (Neşe Atabey)
09:30 - 10:15	<i>Principles of Biobanking in Human Biospecimens</i> Markus Pasterk
10:15 - 10:45	Coffee Break
11:20 - 11:55	<i>Ethical Concepts for Biobanking</i> Mats Hansson
11:55- 12:30	<i>QMS for Biobanking</i> Andrea M. Wutte
12:30-13:05	<i>Data and Database Management and Security for Biobanks</i> Heimo Müller
13:05 - 14:00	LUNCH
14:00 – 16:00	<i>PANEL: Establishment of a Modern Biobank: Session 1</i> Moderator: Uğur Özbek, Turkey Rania Labib, Egypt Imane Cherkaoui - Morocco Maher Sughayer – Jordan Ada Al-Qunaibet – Saudi Arabia
16:00 – 16:30	Coffee break
16:30 - 18:00	<i>PANEL: Establishment of a Modern Biobank: Session 2</i> Moderator: Uğur Özbek, Turkey Sibel Uğur İşeri– Turkey Said Ismail, Qatar Yosr Hamdi - Tunisia
19:00	Dinner

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON BIOBANKING FOR RARE DISEASES
May 3rd, 2018

09:00 - 09:30	Introduction and Group Formation
09:30 - 12:00	<i>Problem Based Learning (PBL) Sessions on Most Frequent Problems in Biobanks</i> Tutors: Uğur Özbek Neşe Atabey Sibel Uğur İşeri Yücel Erbilgin Yavuz Oktay
12:00 - 12:30	Group Discussions
12:30 - 13:30	LUNCH
13:30 - 17:00	Real Workflow in a Biobank
13:30 - 14:15	<i>Taking informed consent for Biobanks: Case studies</i> Görsev Yener, Nur Arslan
14:15 - 14:45	<i>Importance of deep phenotyping for biobanking: A case study</i> Neşe Direk
14:45 - 15:15	<i>Sample transport, registration and sample processing</i> Yavuz Oktay
15:15 - 15:35	Coffee Break
15:35 - 16:05	<i>Generation of patient-specific induced pluripotent stem cell lines for rare genetic diseases: Biobanking perspective</i> Tamer Önder
16:05 - 16:35	<i>Tissue Biobanking</i> Ayça Erşen Danyeli
16:35 - 17:05	<i>A living biobank of Cancer Organoids and Patient Derived Xenograft (PDX) models to reduce high attrition rates in drug discovery</i> Haluk Yüzügüllü
17:05 - 17:35	<i>QC&QM: Best Practices</i> Sibel Uğur İşeri
17:35 - 18:05	<i>Access&Distribution of Biospecimens: Practical Issues</i> Yücel Erbilgin
18:05 - 18:15	Closing Remarks
19:30	Gala Dinner

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON BIOBANKING FOR RARE DISEASES
02 - 03 May 2018 - Izmir, Turkey
www.biobank.gen.tr/biobankworkshop

Quality Management
Information Technologies
Ethical, Legal, and Societal Implications

This workshop is co-funded by a European Commission H2020 project, ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC under grant nr 676550.

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Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
European Research Infrastructure Consortium
BBMRI.tr
Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure of Turkey
IBG
Izmir Biomedicine and Genome Center

REGISTRATION
Application Deadline: 26 March 2018
Evaluation Announcement: 02 April 2018

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SYMPOSIUM BRIDGING BIOBANKS IN MENA COUNTRIES TO PROMOTE RESEARCH AND HEALTHCARE
04 May 2018 - Izmir, Turkey
www.biobank.gen.tr/bridgingbiobanks

Quality
Sustainability
Governance
R&D
IT
ELSI
Storage
Access
Patient
R&D
Clinical
Biobank

This symposium is co-funded by a European Commission H2020 project, ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC under grant nr 676550.

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BBMRI.tr
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REGISTRATION
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Speakers list

Speakers		Talk
Ada Al-Qunaibet	King Abdullah International Medical Research Center, Saudi Arabia	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00
Ali Osman KILIÇ	Karadeniz Technical University	symposium May 4th 14:20-15:00
ANDREA M. WUTTE	BBMRI-ERIC, Austria	workshop, May 2nd 11:55-12:30 Symposium May 4th 11:30-12:00
Ayça Erşen Danyeli	Acıbadem Health Group, Turkey	workshop, May 3rd 16:05-16:35
Dominic Sobczak	ESFRI Executive Secretary	symposium May 4th 09:30-10:00
Fahrettin Keleştemur	TUSEB, Turkey	symposium May 4th 14:20-15:40
Görsev Yener	Dokuz Eylul Faculty of Medicine, Turkey	workshop, May 3rd 13:30-14:15
Haluk Yüzügüllü	In vivo Bioscience, Oncology, AstraZeneca, USA	workshop + symposium May 4th 11:00-11:30
HEIMO MULLER	Medical University of Graz, Austria	workshop, May 2nd 12:30-13:00 Symposium May 4th 12:30-13:00
Imane Cherkoui	Université Mohammed V Souissi (UM5S) Rabat, Morocco	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00 Symposium 16:00-16:30
Jale Şahin	Tubitak, EMBO, ERA-NET	symposium May 4th 14:00-14:20
Kurt Zatloukal	Medical University of Graz, Austria	symposium May 4th 10:00-10:30
MAHER SUGHAYER	King Hussein Cancer Center, Jordan	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00
MARKUS PASTERK	BBMRI-ERIC, Graz Austria	workshop, May 2nd 09:30-10:15
MATS HANSSON	Uppsala University, Sweden	workshop, May 2nd 12:30-13:05 symposium 12:00-12:30
Meral Özgüç	Hacettepe University, Turkey	symposium May 4th 15:00-15:40
Murat Özgören	ESFRI Delegate of Turkey	symposium May 4th 09:00-09:30
Neşe Direk	Dokuz Eylul Faculty of Medicine, Turkey	workshop, May 3rd 14:15-14:45
Nur Arslan	Dokuz Eylul Faculty of Medicine, Turkey	workshop, May 3rd 13:30-14:15
RANIA LABIB	Children's Cancer Hospital, Egypt	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00
Said İsmail	Qatar Genome Program Manager	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00 Symposium 16:30-17:00
Sibel Uğur İşeri	Aziz Sancar Institute of Experimental Medicine	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00+ workshop, May 3rd 17:35-18:05
UĞUR ÖZBEK	Acıbadem University, Turkey	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00
Yavuz Oktay	Izmir Biomedicine and Genome Center, Turkey	workshop, May 3rd 14:45-15:15
Yosr Hamdi	Laval University , ULAVAL , Jordan	workshop, May 2nd 14:00-17:00
Yücel Erbilgin	Aziz Sancar Institute of Experimental Medicine	workshop, May 3rd 17:35-18:05

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Appendix V ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC Biobanking workshop in Latin America

Agenda

ADOPT WORKSHOP RIO DE JANEIRO

2019/01/15-17

Venue: Hotel Windsor Barra

Address: Av. Lúcio Costa, 2630 - Barra da Tijuca, Rio de Janeiro - RJ, 22620-172, Brazil

Phone: +55 21 2195-5000

Agenda

January 15th, hand on

08.30-09.00	Registration	
09.00 – 09.30	Welcome and opening	Erik Steinfeld / Gilberto Domont
09.30 – 09.50	Introduction round	
09.50 – 10.20	Introduction BBMRI-ERIC, ADOPT	Anna-Liisa Bader
10.20 – 10.45	Coffee break	
10.45 – 11.45	<p><i>Session 1: the role of Biobanking in Modern Medicine</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>The Clinical Need (Now&Future) of biobanking</i> <i>Making new treatments possible: Biobanking infrastructure to meet the capacity and build needed</i> 	Johan Malm Gyorgy Marko-Varga, Erik Steinfeld
11.45 – 12.30	Have your say: the audience replies to the key questions in biobanking - Interactive Panel discussion	Francesco Florindi
12.30 – 13.30	Lunch	
13.30 – 14.30	<p><i>Session 2: examples from local biobanks</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>BBMRI.be – a country perspective on driving high quality samples</i> <i>Local expertise - LATAM biobank presenter</i> 	Annelies Debucquoy Alicia A. Colombo Flores
14.30 – 15.30	Distribution game workshop - The purpose of the game is to understand the distribution side dynamics of a multi-echelon supply chain used to distribute a single item	Erik Steinfeld
15.30 – 16.00	Coffee break	
16.00 – 17.00	Conclusions	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 676550.

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19.00 Dinner at Esplanada Grill Barra

Rua Professor Coutinho Fróis, 10 - Barra da Tijuca

Rio de Janeiro - RJ, 22620-360, Brazil

Day 2 - January 16th Applied

09.00 – 09.30	Data collection and management; lessons learned from the CRC cohort	Anna-Liisa Bader
09.30 – 10.00	Ethical aspects and Patient Involvement	Francesco Florindi
10.00 – 10.30	Biobank Mexico	Prof. Hugo Alberto Barrera
10.30 – 11.00	Genomics and Proteomics; European Cancer Moonshot	Gyorgy Marko Varga
11.00 – 13.30	Networking Session – Discussions with Lunch	Erik Steinfeld
13.30 – 14.00	Importance of strategic partnerships – A Dutch approach to internationalization	Bart Scheerder
14.00 – 15.00	Latin American Biobanks to present their projects	
14.30 – 15.00	BBMRI support opportunities for Brazil	Erik Steinfeld
15.00 – 15.30	Coffee break	
15.30 – 16.00	Have your say – 2: the audience replies to the key questions in biobanking - Interactive Panel discussion	Francesco Florindi
16.00 – 16.20	Wrap up and closure	

19.00 Dinner at the Hotel

Day 3- January 17th Applied

10.00 – 10.20	The Antidoping Control Laboratory	Francisco Radler
10:20 - 11:00	Visit to the Laboratory	LBCD team
11.00 – 11.30	Coffee break	
11:30 – 12.00	Open Discussion- <i>Biobanks in Brazil: problems, needs, perspectives</i>	All participants
12.00 – 12.15	Wrap up and closure	BBMRI team & participants

12.30 VISIT TO CORCOVADO (Christ, The Redeemer)

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Attendance list

ADOPT WORKSHOP RIO DE JANEIRO

2019/01/15

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Phone: +55 21 2195-5000

Attendance List

	Name	Organisation	Signature
1	Anne Lagomarcho	U. Chile	<i>anne</i>
2	Fabio CS Maciel	UF RJ	<i>Fabio</i>
3	Luís Felipe C. Ramos	UF RJ	<i>Luís Felipe C. Ramos</i>
4	Raiane de Lucca	UF RJ	Raiane Lucca
5	Michelle K. Martins	UF RJ	<i>Michelle</i>
6	ELIZABETH MUXFELDT	UF RJ	<i>Eli</i>
7	Monica Jéhi F. Alves	ICESP - USP	<i>Monica</i>
8	Miyuki Uno	ICESP - USP	<i>Miyuki</i>
9	ADRIANA CAROLI - BOTTINO	DEPTO. PATOLOGIA UF RJ	<i>Adriana</i>
10	Natália Rêgo de Almeida	UF RJ	Natália Rêgo de Almeida
11	Enka Velasquez	UF RJ	Enka Velasquez
12	Barbro Scheeder	UMCC	<i>Barbro</i>
13	MaTernade Vilarel	Giint	<i>MaTernade</i>
14	Paulo HOLLANDA	BIOQUANTIS	<i>Paulo</i>
15	GUSTAVO MOPPONA	UF RJ	<i>Gustavo</i>

16 GUSTAVO STEFANOFF INCA/ES
 17 DOUGLAS CARVALHO
 BRUNO - ERIC

	Name	Organisation	Signature
16	Yara Martins da Silva	UFRJ	Yara Martins da Silva
17	GEISA PAULINO CAPRIVI EVARILTO	UFRJ	[Signature]
18	Joseph L. M. Evaristo	UFRJ	[Signature]
19	GEORGE MARTINO-CARVALHO	LU	[Signature]
20	Verena DENNINGHOFF	CSMLC	[Signature]
21	Antonio Henrique	Rolle / Leibniz	[Signature]
22	Thair Amorim	Fiocruz / UPPAR	[Signature]
23	FRANCISCO ECONOMI	BBMRI-ERIC	[Signature]
24	JUENAL Pires L	MINSA / GENILE	[Signature]
25	Patricio Aranceda	BTUCH	[Signature]
26	Flávia Bonavent	UFPR	[Signature]
27	BRUNO AYES SILVA	FIOCRUZ / IOC	[Signature]
28	Johan Malin	Lund University	[Signature]
29	Daniel Zang	Innovcell	[Signature]
30	VICTORIA SUNDEN	EBYNE-COVICET	[Signature]
31	Claudia Srenon	USP	[Signature]
32	FABIANA VASCONCELOS M.	UFRO	[Signature]
33	Alvaro Abreu	BTUCH	[Signature]
34	Travis Collier	BTUCH	[Signature]

	Name	Organisation	Signature
35			
36	José Herranz		
37	Manuela Almeida	Fiocruz	
38	Daniela Corrales Paredes	BTUCh	
39	JUAN C. ROA	PUC - CHIR	
40	Diego Romero	PUC - Chile	
41	Pamela Bocchieri	BTUCh	
42	ANNA-LISA BADER	BBMRI	
43	CUSTAVO RINALHO C. DOS SANTOS	UBCO	
44	Erik Skerfvelde	BBMRI-ERIC	
45	Roberto Herai	PUCPR	
46	Felipe Vace	UNAM	
47	Carla Caroline Wagner	BioBanco Barretos	
48	Mariana R. Bottem	HCPA	
49	Fernando Sales S.L. Viana	HCPA	
50	NICOLE WOLDMAR	UFRJ	
51	Sandra Perdomo	U. Bosque	
52	Luc Ma. Ruiz Gady	Instituto Nacional de Cancerología	
53	Elesia Alcalde	Hosp Luis Calvo Mackenna	
54	Anelies Debucquoy	BBMRI-be	

55. Liliana Stedje FLACETS
 56. Joiza Lins Camargo HCPA - Porto Alegre
 57. Lilian Bresson Fiocruz
 58 - Ricardo Cristiano de Souza Bresson
 Bio-Manguinhos

- 59 Hugo A Barrera - Saldes ~~MEXICO~~ - Mexico D.F.
- 60 Mónica Valdés H. ~~MEXICO~~
- 61 LUCIANA PIZZATI BRAZIL - UFPA.
- 62 MARIA DE FATIMA MELO BRAZIL - UFPA.

ADOPT WORKSHOP RIO DE JANEIRO

2019/01/16

16/ene/19.

Venue: Hotel Windsor Barra

Address: Av. Lúcio Costa, 2630 - Barra da Tijuca, Rio de Janeiro - RJ, 22620-172, Brazil

Phone: +55 21 2195-5000

Attendance List

	Name	Organisation	Signature
1	Bart Scherden	UMCG	
2	PAULO HOLANDA	BIOQUANTIS	
3	Lez Ma Ruiz Galoy	Instituto Nacional de Cancerologia	
4	Raiane de lucca	UFRJ	Raiane lucca
5	Pilberto Dorval	UFRJ	
6	Luis Felipe Ramos	UFRJ	
7	Michelle R. Martins	UFRJ	
8	Yara Martins da Silva	UFRJ	
9	Amelies Debucqros	BBMRI-be	
10	Giorgio Maria Varga	LU-SWE	
11	Johan Malin	Lund Univ.	
12	Anne Lagomarcho	Universidad Chile	
13	BRUNO ALVES SILVA	RIOCRUZ	
14	Monique Albert	Ontario Institute for Cancer Research / ICRBC	
15	Claudia Sienora	FMU'61	

16/1/19

	Name	Organisation	Signature
16	Cidriana Landi-Bottino	Dep'to. of Pathology UFRJ	[Signature]
17	Hugo A Banaes	Mexico NRC	[Signature]
18	Fabiola Vasquez Hondo	UFRO- CHILE	[Signature]
19	Elisa Alcalde	HLORI- CHILE	[Signature]
20	Valerie DENNING	HOPE CENTRE	[Signature]
21	Liliana V Sierra	FLACE IS	[Signature]
22	VICTORIA JUNDISUS	INSYNE-COMICET	[Signature]
23	Juan Carlos	BRUCH	[Signature]
24	Gele Corralis	UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL	[Signature]
25	MIYUKI UNO	ICESP-USP	[Signature]
26	Antonio Hugo Campos	Rede D'OR	[Signature]
27	Deanna G. de Jesus	ICESP-USP	[Signature]
28	Roberto H. Herai	PUCPR	[Signature]
29	Fernando Villanar	Asim/Indatoc	[Signature]
30	Fabiana Alencar	BRUCH	[Signature]
31	JUVENAL Pinos	MINSAL/CHILE	[Signature]
32	Thais Amorim	FIOCRUZ	[Signature]
33	Mariana R. Botton	HCPA	[Signature]
34	JUAN CESAR	PUC	[Signature]

(*)

(*) *Procedimientos de Etica de la Investigacion a Salud*

35	Name	Organisation	Signature
36	GUSTAVO RAMALHO	LBCCD / IQ / UFRJ	
37	GEISA PAULINO C. EVARISTO	UFRJ	
38	Joseph G. M. Evaristo	LHDETEC	
39	FABIO CS NEGUEMA	UERJ	
40	Sandra Perdomo	U. Boquete	
41	NICOLE WOLDMAR	UFRS	
42	FERNANDA SILVIANA	HCPA	
43	MARIA DE FATIMA MELO	UFRJ	
44	Zafreio Azenedo	BTUCH	
45	Pamela Bocchieri	BTUCH	
46	Daniela Cavalcanti	BTUCH	
47	Joiza Lins Camargo	HCPA - PA	
48	Franческа Florina	BBMRI-ERIC	
49	Diego Romero	PUC	
50	Andre Cassiano Nuber	Banquetos Ojman Hospital	
51	Natalia P. de Almeida	UFRS	
52	Felipe Vucer	UNAM	
53	Lilian Bressan	Fiocruz	
54	ANNA-LISA BADER	BBMRI-ERIC	
	Eric Skrifvars	BBMRI-ERIC	
	GUSTAVO STEFANOFF	INCA	

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Attendance List

ANTI-DOPING LAB

17.01

	Name	Organisation	Signature
1	Fernanda S L Vianna	Hospital Clínicas PAlegre	FLV
2	Joia Lins CAMARGO	Hospital Clínicas Porto Alegre	[Signature]
3	Mariana R. Botton	Hospital Clínicas Porto Alegre	Mariana Botton
4	ELIZABETH MULESIST	MUCFF-UF RJ	[Signature]
5	Valério D. N. Hoff	COFIC	[Signature]
6	Annelies Debucquoy	BBMRI-be	[Signature]
7	Hugo A Barron	Mexico-NBL	H.A.B.
8	Victoria Sundblad	IBYTE-CONICET	[Signature]
9	Luz Ma. Ruiz Gámez	INCa Mexico	[Signature]
10	FABIO CS NOGUEIRA	UFES	FABIO SN
11	Luís Felipe Ramos	UF RJ	[Signature]
12	Michelle R. Mantim	UF RJ	[Signature]
13	Raiane de Lucca	UFES	Raiane Lucca
14	Elisa Alcalde	HLCM	[Signature]
15	Carlos Comoro	HLCOMACKONNA	[Signature]

	Name	Organisation	Signature
16	Roberto A. Horai	PUCPR	
17	Grupo Cardiológico	Faculdade de Ciências Hospital	
18	Ma. Fernanda Vilhena		
19	Salvador Díaz de León Valdés	Edut. CORINTER	
20	Mónica Valdés Huerta	Edut. CORINTER	
21	Bart Scheerder	UMCG	
22	Johann Malin	Lund Univ	
23	Yara Martins da Silva	UFERS	
24	Diego Romero	PUC Chile	
25	Daniela Carrasco	BTU CH	
26	Pamela Bocchioni O.	BTU CH	
27	Viridiana Beltran	BBMRI	
28	Erik Steinfeldt	BBMRI	
29	Anna-Liisa Eder	BBMRI	
30	Francesco Florindi	BBMRI	
31	Gilberto		
32	Georgy +1		
33	Johan +1		
34	Felipe Vaca	UNAM	

35	Name	Organisation	Signature
36	Sandra Perdomo	U. El Zouge	<i>[Signature]</i>
37	João Henrique	BBMRI	<i>[Signature]</i>
38	Luz María Ruiz Gato	INCan México	<i>[Signature]</i>
39	Carlos Augusto L. Oliveira	IQ-UFRJ	<i>[Signature]</i>
40	Miyuki Uno	ICESP-USP	<i>[Signature]</i>
41	Stevan Jovic-Hor	ICESP-USP	<i>[Signature]</i>
42	Anne Lagomarcino	U Chile	<i>[Signature]</i>
43	Marta Gualberto	HUCAR/UFRJ BRAZIL	<i>[Signature]</i>
44	Alexis Coimbra	BTUC H	<i>[Signature]</i>
45	BRUNO LIVES DA SILVA	FIOCRUZ	<i>[Signature]</i>
46	<p>MAKING NEW TREAT MENTS POSSIBLE</p> <p>email . raiane.lucca@hotmail.com raiane.lucca@eq.ufrj.br</p>		
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ADOPT WORKSHOP RIO DE JANEIRO

2019/01/17

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Attendance List

VISIT TO THE CHRIST
 17.01

	Name	Organisation	Signature
1	Annelies Debucquoy	BBMRI.be	
2	Hugo Aparicio S	MEXICO-NBL	
3	Valer Danimboff	CEIC	
4	VICTORIA SUNDSTAD	IBYNE-COMIET	
5	Luz María Ruiz Godoy	INCan México	
6	Fabrizio Urbizuaré	UFRO- Chile	
7	Jorge Gonzalez	HLC OROCKENPA	
8	Roberto A. Arazi	PUCPR	
9	Anna Carolina Nuber	Barroto's Côrrea Hospital	
10	Salvador Díaz de León Valdés	EDIT CORINTER	
11	Mónica Valdés Huerta	EDIT CORINTER	
12	Bart Scherren	UMC U	
13	Johan Malm	Lund Univ.	
14	Daniela Canoseo	BTUCH	
15	Pamela Bocchioni O.	BTUCH	

	Name	Organisation	Signature
16	Erik Steinfeldt	BBMRI	
17	Viridiana Beltran	BBMRI	
18	Francesco Florindi	BBMRI	
19	Anna-Liisa Bader	BBMRI	
20	Gilberto		
21	Johan + 1		
22	Georgy + 1		
23	Juan Gallegos	BSTUCH	
24	Felipe Vaca	UNAM Mex.	
25	Toni Herranz	BTV CH	
26	GUSTAVO RAMALHO	UNICAMP/UFPA	
27	Natália Pinho de Almeida	UFES	
28	Yara Martins da Silva	UFRJ	
29	Luís Felipe Costa Ramos	UFRJ	
30	NICOLE RODRIGUES	UFES	
31	Michelle R Martins	UFPA	
32	Luzka Ruiz Gody	INCAE México	
33	Miyuki Uno	ICESP-USP	
34	Marina José F. Alves	ICESP-USP	

35	Name	Organisation	Signature
36	BRUNO ALVES DA SILVA	FIOCRUZ	
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Presentations

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 676550.

MAKING NEW TREATMENTS POSSIBLE

INTRODUCTION TO ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
ANNA-LISA BADER

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

WELCOME TO RIO

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

PRACTICAL INFORMATION

- Please keep all the originals of your receipts!
- Please send us the receipts by post after the workshop; if possible, please scan them as well, so we have back-up.
- We need the receipts as soon as possible to start with the reimbursement.
- If you have any questions or concerns, please don't hesitate to ask our team!

Erik Steinfeld Francesco Fiorindi Anna-Lisa Bader Viridiana Beltran

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
IMPLEMENTATION AND OPERATION OF THE GATEWAY TO HEALTH INTO BBMRI-ERIC

- Starting date: 01.10.2015
- Duration: 42 months (ending 31.03.2019)
- The aim of the project is to boost and accelerate implementation of BBMRI-ERIC and its services.
- BBMRI-ERIC will provide a gateway access to the collections of the European research community, expertise and services building on the outcome of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

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MAKING NEW TREATMENTS POSSIBLE

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC: BUILDING THE CRC COHORT
ANNA-LISA BADER

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

COLORECTAL CANCER COHORT
Goal: 10 000 datasets from all over Europe

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

DATA ITEMS

Default variables:

- Sex
- Participation in clinical study
- Age at primary diagnosis
- Known risk factors for CRC
- Time of recurrence (date/year) and availability of biological material from recurrence (if recurrence occurred)
- Vital status and survival information
- Percentage of last episode of vital status
- Overall survival status
- Molecular markers (if applicable)
 - MicrorRNA stability (if applicable)
 - Mitochondrial gene expression - 18S array for different genes (optional but if applicable)
 - BRCA mutations (if applicable)
 - BRCA1/2 mutations (if applicable)
 - BRCA1/2 mutations status (optional)
- Immunotherapy past:
 - TNBS
 - 180C staging
 - 180D grading
 - Biological type of the cancer
 - Localization
 - Metastasis
 - High resolution (40x, 10x, < 0.125um/px) digital images preferably from laser view here
 - Year of sample acquisition (Indicate absolute date - ± 1 year accuracy is sufficient - to assess how old the material is)
- Diagnostic mass:
 - Cytology
 - Any of diagnostic methods (Irrig, biopsy, long biopsy, MRI, CT) done within the context of primary diagnosis
 - CRC Cohort does not collect data from these diagnostic methods, only information on their availability (i.e. they may be requested from the biobank by researchers)

Surgery

- Time difference between initial diagnosis and surgery
- Surgery modality
- Type of surgery

Pharmacotherapy

- REQUIRED if occurred
- Date of start
- Schedule of pharmacotherapy (including textual descriptions of each scheme that doesn't fit into the provided list of schemes)

Targeted therapy

- REQUIRED if occurred
- Date of start
- Date of end

Radiation therapy

- REQUIRED if occurred
- Date of start
- Date of end

Response to therapy

- The response is linked to the patient and specified by a histologist. This is to avoid need to specify in which therapy the response is, since there might be combination of different therapies.

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC
gateway for health

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Colorectal cancer as primary diagnosis
- Available surgical material
- Availability of all REQUIRED Data
- Willingness to provide access

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**MAKING
NEW TREATMENTS
POSSIBLE**

BBMRI.BE
 A COUNTRY PERSPECTIVE ON DRIVING HIGH QUALITY SAMPLES
 ANNELE'S DEBUCCOQY

**WHERE
WE ARE**

**MEMBERS OF
BBMRI-ERIC**

- Austria
- Belgium
- Czech Republic
- Estonia
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Italy
- Lithuania
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Norway
- Poland
- Sweden
- United Kingdom

**OBSERVERS OF
BBMRI-ERIC**

- Switzerland
- Cyprus
- Turkey
- Ukraine

BBMRI.BE

3 Languages - 5 Governments

- ✓ Federal government
- ✓ Flemish government
- ✓ Government of the French Community
- ✓ Government of the German-speaking Community
- ✓ Government of the Walloon Region
- ✓ Government of the Brussels-Capital Region

Three Belgian biobank networks

BIOTHEQUE
WALLOONIE BRUXELLES

- Network of 9 biobanks in Wallonia/ Brussels
- To promote bio-medical research in Wallonia and Brussels
- With a strong emphasis on collaboration with bio-medical industries
- <http://www.biotheque-walloonie-bruxelles.be/>

FEDERALE
FEDERALE

- Virtual network of 11 Belgian biobanks
- Nationwide data of residual human tumour samples in a database
- Catalogue for researchers to search the coded database
- <https://virtualltumourbank.kankerregio.be/>

CMI
Flemish Biobank Initiative

- Network of 5 Flemish biobanks
- Multicenter disease oriented research-network:
 - Sudden Cardiac Death
 - Diabetes
 - Hepatotropic Disorders
 - Rheumatoid Arthritis
 - Inflammatory Bowel Disease

**Biobank as a platform for
biomedical research**
1st Biobank in Mexico

Dr. Luz Ma. Ruiz Godoy Rivera
Biobank INCan Coordinator

BIOBANK

- In 1998, four pathologists started this project: Dr. Meneses, Dr. Mohar, Dr. Suárez and myself. Yet the necessary budget wasn't available to develop a biobank. After discussion and meeting, I was assigned to coordinate the project in 2007.
- The first steps were to:
 - Adapt the area, the facilities and the manual of procedures.
 - Create a new way of getting informed consent, validated by the INCan bioethics committee.

BIOBANK

- I started the project in 2008. We began to collect tissue samples and made tests with histological and molecular quality control. This process was certified by ISO 9001-2008 and the date remains certified over time.
- In December of the same year, the first meeting of tumor banks of the Biobanking Network / Tumor Banks of Latin America and the Caribbean (REBLAC) was held in Rio de Janeiro. Our biobank participated in this meeting as a representation of the first biobank in Mexico.

Ethical & legal aspects

No current Legislation for Biobanks.

Yes Law on Donation and Transplants

Yes, National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedics

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

MEXICO BIOBANK NETWORK

Dr. Hugo A. Barrera-Saldaña
Coordinator
Innbiogen, SC
Monterrey, MÉXICO

RESEARCH TO DISCOVER AND TO TRANSLATE

CHALLENGE:
"It is well known that children born without the *IGF1R* gene don't respond to the injected hormone, because their immune systems don't recognize it and thus induce antibodies against it"

American Journal of Medical Genetics 72:399-402 (1997)

TRANSLATE TO SERVE: MDx SERVICES

Molecular Diagnostic Unit at UANL

- Cystic fibrosis
- Hemophilia A
- D/B muscular dystrophies
- Sickle cell anemia
- Factor V (Leiden)
- Neural tube defects (MTHFR)
- Hemochromatosis
- Pituitary dwarfism
- Infertility (deletions in Y chr.)
- Philadelphia chr.
- p53 mutations
- Ras mutations
- Adenovirus
- Cytomegalovirus
- Human papilloma virus
- Human Immunodeficiency Virus
- Hepatitis B Virus
- Hepatitis C Virus

Start-up incubated at UANL

Vitagénesis

K-ras test

Sample: PEFF tumor biopsy accompanied by slide with tumor area identified by pathologist.

Method: DNA extraction, PCR amplification of K-ras gene and Sanger sequencing of clinically relevant gene codons.

RESULT: Non mutated

RESULT: Mutated

MOLECULAR GENETICS SERVING NE-MEXICO POPULATION

MAKING TRANSLATIONAL MEDICAL RESEARCH TRULY BIDIRECTIONAL

Services	Patients/year
Consultations	268,189
Surgeries	13,243
Laboratory tests	613,929
Pathology tests	23,263

CLINICAL DEPTS:

- Oncology
- Dermatology
- Psychiatry
- Pediatrics
- Allergies
- Nephrology
- Rheumatology
- Infectious Diseases
- Urology
- Ophthalmology
- Hematology
- Respiratory
- Gynecology
- Gastroenterology

- ✓ >10 years
- ✓ Mol Biol analyses
- ✓ 14 projects
- ✓ 12 thesis
- ✓ 4 int. collaborations
- ✓ >2,000 patients
- ✓ >5,000 aliquots:
 - 34% DNA
 - 58% serum or plasma
 - 7% FFPE and fresh
 - 1% eye samples

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

<p>umcg lifelines BiKE</p> <p>Role of Strategic Partnerships A Dutch Perspective</p> <p><i>Bart Scheerder</i> <i>Senior Consultant Biobanking & International Strategy and Relations, UMG</i> <i>ADOPT meeting Rio de Janeiro, 16 January 2019</i></p>	<p>Disclaimer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UMG has strategic partners in Chile, Brazil, Colombia and Mexico • Biobanks can provide an excellent resource to build collaborative research • There are upcoming EU-Latin American research grant opportunities • It is in my interest that a pan-Latin American biobank network is created (using BBMRI-ERIC's example)
<p>Hard work will pay off.</p>	

<p>The Clinical Need "NOW & FUTURE" of BIOBANKING</p> <p>Gyorgy Marko-Varga <i>*Lund University Hospital</i> <i>*Lund University</i> <i>*Tokyo Medical, Japan</i> <i>*Yonsei University, Seoul, Korea</i></p> <p>Bio-banking capacity for Many Millions of sample storage repository</p>	
<p>The Clinical Need "NOW & FUTURE" of BIOBANKING</p> <p>"One Billion \$ Question"</p> <p>Baseline Day 15 PET Scan</p>	

**Building a smart and integrated Biobank:
The experience of the University of Chile Biobank**

Alicia Colombo, PhD.
 Scientific Director
 University of Chile Biobank
 (UChBiobank)

UChBiobank

La Universidad de Chile inauguró el Biobanco de tejidos de la Facultad de Medicina de la U. de Chile.

The University of Chile Biobank was formed at the end of 2012 thanks to a joint effort of the Faculty of Medicine and the Clinical Hospital of the University of Chile

Our Mission

The mission of our Biobank is to act as the University of Chile center for biological samples and health information to enable research towards the discovery and development of new healthcare tools.

Organization Chart

To fulfill our mission, we are organized according to the following scheme:

The role of Biobanking in Modern Medicine

Adopt Workshop Rio de Janeiro

2019/01/15-17

Johan Malm, MD, PhD

Professor in Clinical Chemistry
 Department of Translational Medicine
 Lund University
 Sweden

Anna Lindh
 Minister for Foreign Affairs, Sweden
 1998 - 2003

Same textile fibre found on knife and cap

Hair ->DNA

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Biobank From Barretos Cancer Hospital

MSc Ana Caroline Neuber
 Biologist/ PhD Student
 carol_neuber@hotmail.com

Link:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=naXpilhurCU>

Biobank from Barretos Cancer Hospital was founded in 2006.

Process biological samples of oncology patients

Storage in ultra-freezers -80°C

Provide high quality samples for research

Total Samples Biobank x Biorepository

Category	Percentage	Number of Samples
Biobank	79%	184,275
Biorepository	21%	47,871
Total		More than 230,000

GRUPO IMPULSO DE INCENTIVACIÓN PARA NUEVAS TECNOLOGÍAS

The revolutionary company in Regenerative Medicine and Biotechnology

Harvard Business Case
 Abraham Franklin
 August 2018

Rapid Growth and Future Milestones

Giint in big picture

Our profit centers

Regenerative treatment/ Network expansion

Clinical Franklin has a sanitary license for the clinical application of mesenchymal stem cells for several conditions (Wellness, Orthopedics, Neuro, Autoimmune, Aesthetic)

Palliative Care program

One disease with fully-phased studies that will become a flagship service and biotechnology product. This will position the company as a specific therapeutic-focused biotech company.

Stem cell drug

Cell product for the treatment of Multiple Sclerosis. Phase I clinical study

Contract manufacturing services

INDEBIOC, avant-garde laboratory, performs the process of expansion (multiplication), analysis and delivery of mesenchymal stem cells of the highest quality for specific medical treatments.

Stem Cell Banking

Store a Cell. Banking service for 6, 11 and 21 years of the mesenchymal cells obtained from dental pulp, adipose tissue, umbilical cord and placenta for its therapeutic use in the future.

Research and licensing

In collaboration with public and private research centers we carry out basic and applied research projects for the development of new cellular technologies promoting the work of Mexican scientists.

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**HUCFF/UFRJ
BIOBANK
IMPLEMENTATION**

ELIZABETH SILAID MUXFELDT
DIRECTOR OF RESEARCH DIVISION
HUCFF/UFRJ

RATIONAL OF THE PROPOSITION
mandatory since 2011

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